

Project Number: 101188015

Start Date of Project: 01/01/2025

Duration: 36 months

Deliverable 2.1

EOSC EDEN Specifications and Architecture (Iteration 1)

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Deliverable	(30/09/25), September (M9)
Actual Submission Date	(30/09/2025)
Work Package	WP2 Long-term Access and Preservation Services & Tools
Task	T2.1 Defining systems requirements and specifications
Type	Report
Version	V1.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.72

Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable presents the first iteration of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) EDEN specifications and architecture for long-term access and preservation services. It consolidates system requirements, repository attributes, and service specifications, aligning them with established standards and frameworks such as Open Archival Information System (OAIS), to enable trusted, interoperable, and scalable preservation infrastructures across diverse scientific domains.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

DELIVERY SLIP

Contribution	Name	Partner	ORCID
Lead author(s)	Wesley Middelbos	CERN	0009-0000-6497-8372
Contributor(s)	Matthew Addis	Arkivum	0000-0002-3837-2526
	Wim Hugo	KNAW-DANS	0000-0002-0255-5101
	Wilko Steinhoff	KNAW-DANS	0000-0003-1106-8441
	Kyle Snyder	SURF	0000-0001-8416-2442
	Marcella Wijngaarden	SURF	0000-0003-2804-4075
	Karl Presser	PMT	0000-0001-7644-4116
	Malwina Cieřła	PMT	0009-0006-7713-2468
	Jean-Yves Le Meur	CERN	0000-0002-9803-6639
	Tiina Koho	CSC	0009-0006-2391-6064
	Johan Kylander	CSC	0000-0002-8084-8233
	Mikko Laukkanen	CSC	n/a
	Juha Lehtonen	CSC	0000-0002-9916-5731
	Mattias Levlin	CSC	0009-0001-4335-8024
	Kris Dekeyser	KU Leuven	0000-0002-7361-5749
	Robert Huber	UBREMEN	0000-0003-3000-0020
	Jens Weiser	UBREMEN	0000-0002-9199-5861
	Svein Høier	UiT	0000-0002-9261-8769
	Bertrand Caron	TIB	0000-0002-3433-9518
Reviewer(s)	Rene van Horik	KNAW-DANS	0000-0001-6899-760X
	Terje Klemetsen	UiT	0000-0002-2024-1798

VERSIONING HISTORY

Version	Date	Description	Author/Editor/Reviewer
v.0.5	22/08/25	First draft	Wesley Middelbos / Inclusive all contributors
v.0.6	04/09/25	First draft - Editorial Review	Wesley Middelbos / Wim Hugo
v.0.8	08/09/25	Final draft - Ready for review	Wesley Middelbos / Wim Hugo
v.0.9	29/09/25	Final version submitted to Project Management Office	Wesley Middelbos / Wim Hugo / Inclusive all contributors
v.1.0	30/09/25	Final version submitted to EC portal	Sara Orhanen, PMO

TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
BCDR	Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics
CCSDS	Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems

D2.1 – EOSC EDEN Specifications and Architecture (Iteration 1)

FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
OAIS	Open Archival Information System
OAIS IF	OAIS Interoperability Framework
OAIS RM	OAIS Reference Model
PDI	Preservation Description Information
RDA TRSP WG	RDA Working Group on Trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers
TDA	Trustworthy Digital Archive
TDR	Trustworthy Digital Repository
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, Technology
TTRAM	Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Objectives	1
1.2	Goals	1
1.3	Relationships to other Work Packages	1
2	Methodology	2
2.1	Approach	2
2.2	Standardised Inventory of Repository Attributes	4
2.3	Registry	4
2.4	Service Specifications	5
2.5	Information Models	5
3	Interoperability	6
3.1	Technical Interoperability	7
3.2	Semantic Interoperability	10
3.3	Organisational Interoperability	13
3.4	Legal Interoperability	16
3.5	Challenges of Archival Information Packages	19
3.5.1	Considerations and Aspects of AIP Interoperability and Exchange	20
3.5.2	Services and Requirements for AIP Interoperability and Exchange	22
4	Quality assurance of research outputs	25
4.1	Contextual Data Quality	26
4.2	Metadata Quality	27
4.3	Technical Data Quality	29
5	Rights & Ethics	32
5.1	Copyright & Law	32
5.2	Licensing and Digital Rights Management	33
5.3	Policy Considerations	35
5.4	Contract / Preservation Agreement	37
5.5	Ethics Considerations	38
6	Services	40
7	Attributes	42
8	Requirements	43
9	Specifications	45
10	Conclusions and Recommendations	47
11	References	49

List of Figures

Figure 2.1.1: Overview of WP2 Methodology	3
Figure 3.1: Generalisation Framework for Interoperability	6
Figure 3.5.1: OAIS Model. Reproduced from the OAIS specification [R32]	20
Figure 3.5.2.1: Example AIP Exchange Workflow and Services	23
Figure 4.1: Scope of Quality Assurance of Research Outputs	25
Figure 5.3.1. Frequency of Occurrence of Policy Groups	36

List of Tables

Table 3.1.1: Technical Interoperability Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification	9
Table 3.2.1: Semantic Interoperability Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification	12
Table 3.3.1: Organisational Interoperability Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification	15
Table 3.4.1: Legal Interoperability Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification	19
Table 3.5.1.1: AIP Considerations: Inventory	21
Table 3.5.1.2: AIP Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification	21
Table 3.5.2.1: AIP Describing services	23
Table 3.5.2.2: AIP Validating services	24
Table 3.5.2.3: AIP Exchanging services	24
Table 4.1.1: Contextual Data Quality: Inventory and Attribute Identification	27
Table 4.2.1: Metadata Quality: Inventory and Attribute Identification	29
Table 4.3.1: Technical Data Quality Aspects: Inventory and Attribute Identification	31
Table 5.1.1: Copyright & Law Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification	33
Table 5.2.1: Licensing and Digital Rights Management Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification	35
Table 5.3.1: Policy Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification	37
Table 5.4.1: Contract/ Preservation Agreement Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification	37
Table 5.5.1: Ethics Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification	39
Table 6.1: Examples of Relevant Services	41
Table 7.1: Attributes	42
Table 8.1. Example Requirements	44
Table 9.1 Example Specifications	46

Executive Summary

The EOSC EDEN project addresses the growing need for sustainable, interoperable, and trusted solutions for digital preservation and access to research outputs. As data volumes increase and disciplinary practices diversify, there is a critical demand for coherent service specifications that enable repositories and infrastructures to operate reliably across domains. This deliverable, produced under Task 2.1 of Work Package 2 (WP2) defines the requirements, attributes and service specifications that will form the foundation of EOSC EDEN's digital preservation and curation services.

The methodology applied in Task 2.1 was iterative and collaborative. It began with a systematic analysis of existing standards, frameworks and practices in digital preservation, ensuring alignment with established community efforts such as the OAIS Reference Model, FAIR principles, and the EOSC Interoperability Framework. This information-gathering phase generated a large set of requirements and identified initial candidate services. These were then refined by mapping them against the Core Preservation Processes (CPPs) defined in WP1 and the domain-specific requirements collected in WP3.

Subsequent analysis of key considerations and aspects led to the identification of additional requirements and new services. Repository attributes were then formalised into a standardised inventory, ensuring consistent descriptions and interoperability across communities. These attributes serve as the foundation for a planned registry that will enable discovery, benchmarking, and evaluation of repositories and services.

Building on these steps, the identified services were structured and, where gaps remained, new services were defined. Service specifications were drafted to describe required functionalities, covering both repository operations and interoperability with external infrastructures. For the first iteration, specifications were drafted for services. These provide a concrete starting point for implementation and validation and further iteration. After reviewing formal output from other projects such as FIDELIS, the selection of services may be adapted; any such modifications will be incorporated into the second interaction of the specification process to ensure alignment with broader EOSC development and community consensus.

Where possible, specifications leverage prior work from initiatives such as FAIR-IMPACT, FAIRCORE4EOSC and the FIDELIS project. Where no adequate solutions exist, Task 2.1 has defined candidate services for proof-of-concept, beta testing, or operational implementation.

1 Introduction

The EOSC EDEN project aims to provide a sustainable, interoperable, and trusted ecosystem for long-term access and preservation of digital research outputs. Within this context, Work Package 2 (WP2) addresses the foundational challenge of defining the requirements, attributes and service specifications needed to ensure that repositories and preservation infrastructures can operate reliably across diverse domains. Task 2.1 plays a central role by consolidating requirements, aligning them with existing standards and frameworks, and translating them into actionable specifications that will underpin subsequent implementation activities across EOSC EDEN.

1.1 Objectives

The objective of Task 2.1 is to define system requirements and specifications necessary to support enhanced and aligned curations, long-term access and preservation services. These specifications are based on the needs identified in WP1, WP3, complemented by external reference models such as OAIS. The task ensures that the resulting service specifications address functional, non-functional and architectural needs across diverse user communities and domains, laying the foundation for implementation in later tasks.

1.2 Goals

The primary goals of T2.1 are to consolidate user and system requirements, translate them into actionable specifications for a service-orientated architecture which is facilitating trusted, scalable, and interoperable preservation and curation services. By providing a coherent foundation, Task 2.1 supports EOSC EDEN partners and third-party service providers in implementing solutions that align with FAIR principles, the EOSC Interoperability Framework, and best practices in digital preservation.

1.3 Relationships to other Work Packages

Task 2.1 is closely related to other EOSC EDEN work packages:

WP1 - Core Preservation Processes: Work Package 1 (WP1) has defined processes. If an archive is following these processes, it could be considered a Trusted Data Archive. Task 2.1 used these processes to extract requirements from them, but also to map to identified services.

WP3 - Discipline-specific Requirements and Validation: Supplies domain-specific and cross-disciplinary requirements, and plays a key role in the creation of tests and validation methods for WP2 outputs to ensure practical relevance across communities.

2 Methodology

2.1 Approach

Work Package 2 in the EDEN project aims to develop the following sets of interrelated outputs in tasks 2.1 and 2.2:

1. An inventory of the design considerations (“considerations”), and their detailed aspects (“aspects”) that are in scope for curation and preservation actions in repositories and archives.
2. A comprehensive inventory of repository attributes, linked where appropriate to object, collection, institutional, or other attributes, and linked to the considerations and aspects as applicable.
3. Such attributes are determined by services, or the attributes describe the nature of the services in use by the repository or archive.
4. The above can be used to elaborate and develop three sets of specifications:
 - a. Specifications for the advertisement and exchange of repository attribute information;
 - b. Specifications for a registry of repositories, its supporting services, and its attributes, and
 - c. Specifications for services that are deemed to be in scope for the EOSC EDEN project, some of which will be implemented by project partners as proofs-of-concept, beta, or operational services.

WP2 does not develop these inventories and specifications in isolation, but draws on significant input from other work packages in the EOSC EDEN project, from work underway in the EOSC FIDELIS project, and from a variety of other HE projects, RDA working groups, and applicable initiatives. These are summarised in Figure 2.1.

The specific input sources that will be considered are:

1. **TRSP WG - RDA:** The [Technical Repository Service Providers](#) Working Group in RDA is compiling a disambiguated and partly mapped foundational attribute set for repositories and repository service providers. This can serve as a basis for our inventory of repository attributes.
 - a. Timeline: Liaise with TRSP WG after publication of this deliverable and contribute to the inclusion of EOSC EDEN attributes to their mapping.
2. **FAIR-IMPACT Repository Attributes:** Recommendations on machine-readable implementation of [DRAWG](#) was developed and specified, together with guidelines for implementation, by the FAIR-IMPACT Work Package 5, and is available for consideration (Task 5.4 - [“Repository Attributes”](#)).
 - a. Timeline: published.
3. **All Compliance Assessment:** A [conceptual Model](#) for encoding of assessment was developed by FAIRCORE4EOSC WP2. The model has been published ([Compliance Assessment Toolkit](#)), and the services for assessment are available, but currently configured for policy compliance assessment.
 - a. Timeline: published and operational.
4. **FAIR Assessment:** OSTrails WP3 is developing specifications for the definition and exchange of FAIR tests, aligned with the FAIRCORE4EOSC Conceptual Model. The project will additionally develop API specifications for FAIR assessment tools, scientific knowledge graphs, and machine-actionable Data Management plans - all in scope and useful for EOSC EDEN ([FAIR](#), [SKG-IF](#), [maDMP](#)).
5. **EOSC FIDELIS:** EOSC FIDELIS WP5 is developing the TTRAM (Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix), which will serve as an additional profile and classification of repository attributes.
6. **EOSC LTDR Task Force:** The EOSC [Long-Term Data Retention](#) Task Force is also defining the guidelines and best practices for appraisal and re-appraisal of objects retained for the long term, and indirectly identifies repository attributes and services in the process. The aim is to produce a [Vocabulary - Q3 2025](#), and report on [Status and Needs - Q4 2025](#).

7. **EOSC Beyond:** The EOSC Beyond project will propose a vocabulary for the description of digital rights, based on the Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) specification but tailored to EOSC repository needs, in September 2026. The landscape analysis informing the design will be published in September 2025. These inputs should be considered in future iterations.

Figure 2.1.1: Overview of WP2 Methodology

In addition to these inputs and considerations, the EOSC EDEN project will contribute directly via

1. **Core Preservation Processes:** Work Package 1 has published a [set of Core Preservation Processes](https://zenodo.org/records/16992452)¹ and its definition ("CPPs"), which will directly assist with the identification of repository attributes and services associated with them.
2. **Expert Input:** The contributors to Work Package 2, in parallel to the other initiatives, are compiling an early draft of their knowledge and experience in respect of repository-related actions, workflows, and quality considerations, and this forms the bulk of the early draft of Deliverable D2.1 (this document).
3. **User Considerations:** Work Package 3 will produce an early input as the results of a desktop study and stand-alone interviews, which can be processed to identify additional repository attributes and services (if any). These will be further refined in M12 of the project.

To compile the necessary information and ultimately identify relevant considerations, aspects, attributes, and both existing and missing services, the task followed a structured, multi-step methodology.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/16992452>

The approach taken can be summarised as:

1. **Information gathering:** Analysing frameworks, formats, processes and standards in digital preservation to establish a comprehensive foundation. This step produced a large set of requirements and identified a first set of services
2. **Requirement Alignment:** Mapping of the collected requirements against the Core Preservation Processes (CPPs) defined in WP1 and mapping of the generalised discipline-specific requirements service form the D3.1 of Work Package 3 [R6].
3. **Considerations & Aspects** - Defining key design considerations and their associated detailed aspects. This analysis generated additional requirements and led to the identification of further services to address the needs.
4. **Attribute identification:** Defining repository attributes and supporting elements to feed into the design of a community registry.
5. **Service structuring and creation:** Consolidation of identified services, aligning them with relevant frameworks, and, where necessary, creating new candidate services. While also mapping these services to the identified requirements and CPPs.
6. **Specification development:** Drafting high-level specifications for defined services, ensuring that they are logically coherent, interoperable, and actionable for implementation across diverse infrastructure.

This iterative cycle, moving from information gathering to requirements and services, then to consideration and aspects, and back to refined requirements and services, ensures that the methodology is both comprehensive and adaptive to changes.

2.2 Standardised Inventory of Repository Attributes

Work Package 2 in EOSC EDEN aims to establish an open-ended² inventory of repository attributes (Appendix A), reflecting the properties of such attributes. These include, but are not limited to, the name and description of the attribute, a stable URI for referencing the attribute, any either URIs that may already be in use for the attribute, and information on its automated determination, benchmarking (if any) and testing, computation or sourcing or attributes.

Standardisation is achieved by providing a comprehensive and stable source of repository attribute definitions and URIs to reference them with. These can be used to unambiguously reference profiles, tests, benchmarks, and guidance related to these attributes.

2.3 Registry

The registry envisaged by EOSC EDEN will allow repositories and their associated and supporting services to be described, characterised, selected, and referenced unambiguously. The registry will be an aggregate of existing repository listings, for example as provided by re3Data and FAIRSharing. The registry is intended as the basis of community and network management envisaged by FIDELIS.

By linking the selection capabilities foreseen in the registry to configured profiles for a specific community or research group, an indirect objective of guiding depositors to the most suitable repository for their research output can be supported.

The design considerations, high-level requirements, and specifications for the registry will be further defined within Task 2.2.

² Open-ended in the sense that the content will not be limited to contributions added during the lifetime of the project, but will continue to be refined, curated, and extended afterwards by an appropriate custodian.

2.4 Service Specifications

Service specifications describe the functionality required for repository operations, interoperability, and quality assurance. Where existing solutions were insufficient, new services were identified as candidates for development within EDEN. These will be further scoped as proofs-of-concept, beta services, or fully operational implementations depending on feasibility and priority.

2.5 Information Models

The Work Package will require definition of the landscape and ecosystem in which it works, and identify and describe the actors and other information models that are involved in workflow processes and provide services. The relevant information models will have to take account of, and to some extent harmonise existing models, vocabularies, and ontologies that deal with the same topics.

We identify the following interdependent information models:

1. **Actors:** The processes implemented by repositories involve many actors, including human ones such as researchers (in more than one role, such as end users or depositors), publishers, certification authorities, curators and repository managers, and system actors such as repositories and their supporting services.
2. **Entities and Attributes:** The actors are associated and interact with a number of entities, including institutions, repositories, collections and groupings within such repositories, and objects or composites of objects deposited and archived within these collections. The entities have relations between them, and the attributes can be aggregated or inherited between related entities.
3. **Registry Conceptualisation:** The EDEN project, via WP2, aims to establish a registry of repositories and their supporting services, and make this useful to those selecting repositories for a specific purpose, while also supporting the presentation, dissemination, and persistence of formal and informal assessments of these repositories against a variety of benchmarks. To support such a registry, we need to define the entities and relations between them - based on the higher-level information models.
4. **Compliance Assessment and Quality Assurance:** The definition and implementation of a standardised terminology for and approach to quality assurance and compliance assessment is desirable and can be based on models and specifications already developed for this purpose.
5. **Repository SKG:** Conceptually, one can define a collection of interlinked Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) that together describe the repository landscape, its characteristics, performance, and associated services. The other information models contribute nodes and/ or relations to this graph. In practice, the graph could be fragmented and/ or federated, but interoperability can be supported by having a common understanding of the nodes and relations, and by provision of inventories of the nodes, their relations, and their properties.

The actors involved in repository-related processes and activities are described in basic terms by the DCAT vocabulary, as well as by the DCAT-AP extensions. These inputs will form the basis of future definition of actors, entities, and the relations between them³.

³ The FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC projects used this as a basis for modelling of the actors and concepts involved in repository-related activities, see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13486326>

3 Interoperability

Work Package 2 in EDEN considers four categories of interoperability:

1. **Technical Interoperability**, in the sense of enabling systems and services, including data repositories, applications, protocols and infrastructures to exchange, communicate and process digital objects without human intervention. While making sure open specifications are used, the use of trusted identifiers, interfaces who are secured and machine-actionable formats are used across organisational and disciplinary boundaries.
2. **Semantic Interoperability**, in the sense of being able to reference and describe repositories, their attributes, and their supporting services using unambiguous registry and vocabulary URIs, and mapping semantic models used in data or metadata schema from one source to another.
3. **Organisational Interoperability**, in the sense of aligning policies, responsibilities and workflows across organisations so that services and infrastructures can collaborate seamlessly.
4. **Legal Interoperability**, in the sense of ensuring that access rights, restrictions, licenses associated with the data and services (such as copyright) are clearly expressed, legally compatible and machine-readable, so that digital objects can be reused and combined across borders and jurisdictions without legal issues.

Figure 3.1: Generalisation Framework for Interoperability

Figure 3.1 generalises the likely interoperability requirements to be identified from user stories and requirements. Generally speaking, repositories ingest, process, archive, and disseminate data and metadata (for example, as defined by [OAIS RM](#) [R32], and by Work Package 1 as the Core Preservation Processes [R26]), and in doing so, they invoke services to assist with quality assurance, transformation, enhancement, and characterisation of data and metadata.

In the generic framework, interoperability specifications address three categories (A), (B), and (C), as indicated in Figure 3.1:

- A. Specifications for the encoding of a 'package', which contains sub-elements of
 - a. Metadata (encoded in any of a number of applicable schemas).
 - b. One or more data files, either by reference or as physical objects, provided in a standardised structure (for example a real or logical folder structure);
 - c. Additional information, dealing with provenance, detailed file-level metadata, and links to or physical copies of other objects of interest, such as code.
- B. Specifications for requests and responses from any number of services that are considered to be in scope. Such service specifications contain service-specific payloads, but need to align with content typically in scope for 'packages', and retain the same definitions and object structures whenever possible. For example, the [MSCR](#)⁴ could be used to transform the source metadata schema to the target schema, and a service such as [DROID](#)⁵ could be used to validate file types.
- C. For each conversion between package specifications, there can be one or more configurations, defining workflows steps (if any), and any other parameters that are required.

The input to the interconversion process can be an unstructured collection of objects, provenance information and metadata, or it can be already structured based on one of a number of standardised package specifications. Likewise, the output will usually be one of these standardised packages, but could also in some cases remain unstructured or partly structured (for example, transforming only the metadata schema).

The output of a specific transformation can serve as the input for another, 'chaining' transformations in cases where this is required.

3.1 Technical Interoperability

Interoperability goes beyond the simple ability to exchange data, it spans multiple layers, enabling systems to exchange, validate and process digital objects over decades without the need of human intervention. As technology is evolving faster than infrastructures can adapt, automating processes so that systems can recognise each other's technologies and interact seamlessly is essential.

This ensures that workflows remain functional even as the underlying technology changes, safeguarding durability and consistency in the exchange, validation and processing of digital objects across diverse communities and systems.

The analysis of the EOSC Interoperability Framework [R27] confirms that many of its recommendations are directly applicable to EOSC EDEN. In the Technical Interoperability layer, the goal is to ensure that digital objects preserved today can still be located, understood and re-used decades from now, regardless of technological shifts or organisational boundaries. This is achieved through the definition and adoption of open technical standards, interoperable interfaces, sustainable identifiers and automated workflows that enable seamless exchange between preservation services and research infrastructures.

The purpose of Technical Interoperability is to make different information systems and/or software applications communicate with each other and be able to share data and accept this data, potentially executing a set of steps which do not require human intervention by an operator.

⁴ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr>

⁵ <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/information-management/manage-information/policy-process/digital-continuity/file-profiling-tool-droid/>

Based on the requirements and recommendations described in the Interoperability Framework of EOSC (being the main reference material), internal sources from the EOSC EDEN project, such as the Core Preservation Processes [R26] (EOSC EDEN WP1) and the Discipline-Specific Requirements [R6] (EOSC EDEN WP3) five considerations were identified, that are described below:

1. Lack of open and uniform interface specifications: Making use of proven protocols, and knowing the interfaces to access data and services can improve interoperability [R27]. APIs may not be aligned with each other and documentation of the interfaces may not be available, which makes interoperability more difficult. Organising a shared set of minimal machine-readable documentation could improve interoperability.

Aspects derived from this consideration are:

- Adoption of open API standards or protocols (e.g., REST, OAI-PMH, OpenAPI)⁶
- Reference implementations and API guidelines⁷

2. Format Fragmentation in Research Data: Being able to handle multiple different file formats is important to creating interoperability. Many communities have their own data formats which makes this a complex problem to solve. Data is coming from a wide variety of sources and different communities. These communities will more often than not have their own specific data formats aside from more generic ones such as CSV, XML, JSON[R6]. As metadata coming from other sources may not be complete, this can become a problem as the preservation system may not know how to handle files anymore. To improve interoperability and sharing the data better, checking the quality of the data format, metadata, documentation, and making it easy to convert between formats or organizing a shared data model are needed.

Aspects derived from this consideration are:

- Support for both general-purpose and domain-specific formats⁸
- Metadata alignment across heterogeneous formats⁹
- Integration tools for bridging formats¹⁰
- Support for different packaging standards¹¹

3. Lack of Federated Discovery Across Domains: Searching for relevant information over multiple communities or repositories is not easy. It often requires authenticating in multiple services, the knowledge of the different querying methods. Interoperability between repositories can partially solve this by allowing data from other communities or repositories which can be in interest for the community the repository is serving to be ingested or served. This way, users of a community can continue using their trusted system while still being able to find related research data[R27].

Aspects derived from this consideration are:

- Top-level and fine-grained search mechanisms¹²

⁶"Give preference to open specifications, taking due account of the coverage of functional needs, maturity and market support and innovation." - [R27] Page 26

⁷"Reuse and share solutions (e.g., software components, Application Programming Interfaces, standards), and cooperate in the development of joint solutions when implementing EOSC services." - [R27] Page 26

⁸"EOSC must enable easy access to data sources available in different formats, either generic or community-based, to facilitate overcoming their heterogeneity and allow integrating data across communities." - [R27] Page 15

⁹"Metadata records of digital objects in repositories ... required by search engines, metadata aggregators, bibliographic cataloguing systems." - [R27] Page 46

¹⁰"Technical interoperability covers the applications ... secure communication protocols." - [R27] Page 11

¹¹"Examples of Digital Objects proposed in ... their implementations (e.g., RO-Crate, the BagIt specification)." - [R27] Page 8

¹²"Coarse-grained and fine-grained dataset (and other research object) search tools need to be made available." - [R27] Page 16

- Federated and cross-domain query support¹³
- Metadata indexing at multiple levels¹⁴
- Discovery APIs supporting varying granularity¹⁵

4. Persistent Identifier (PID) Diversity and Policy Gaps: Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are ensuring consistent and unambiguous referencing to digital objects. As there are many different standards for PIDs, with differences between them. To improve interoperability, it is important to have a clear and consistent PID policy. It is because of that it is recommended to adopt widely used schemas such as DOI or ORCID[R27].

Aspects derived from this consideration are:

- Cross-community PID harmonisation¹⁶
- Machine-resolvable PIDs¹⁷
- Metadata-linked identifiers¹⁸
- Clear EOSC PID policy and lifecycle tracking¹⁹

5. Standards-Based Authentication Mechanisms: To ensure seamless and secure access to EOSC services across platforms and institutions, authentication must rely on widely adopted, standards-based protocols such as SAML, OpenID Connect, and OAuth2. These protocols enable federated identity, machine-to-machine trust, and secure API access, all of which are crucial for automated workflows and cross-service interoperability. Proper implementation of these mechanisms reduces integration effort, improves security, and aligns with the EOSC Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI)[R27].

In table 3.1.1 three informative example aspects connected to technical interoperability are listed. A list of all the identified aspects can be found in Appendix C or in the spreadsheet²⁰.

Table 3.1.1: Technical Interoperability Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Identified attributes
Format Fragmentation in Research Data	Support for both General-purpose and Domain-specific Formats	Does the repository publish information about which type of data and which formats it supports for preservation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishes which types of information the repository stores in a machine-readable interface. (software, analysis, raw data) • Publish policies and refer them with persistent URI about formatting of file formats to a desired type by the repository
Format Fragmentation in Research Data	Metadata Alignment across Heterogeneous Formats	Does the repository support the ability to map, transform and/or align metadata that comes in different schemas,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishes a list of supported metadata schemas • Publishes a list which metadata schemas can be crosswalked

¹³"Need for federated access over existing research data repositories (both inside a discipline and across disciplines)." - [R27] Page 17

¹⁴"A minimum metadata model should be proposed in the future to ease discovery over existing federated research data and metadata." - [R27] Page 17

¹⁵"EOSC must enable easy access to data sources available in different formats... to facilitate overcoming their heterogeneity and allow integrating data across communities." - [R27] Page 15,16

¹⁶"There is a need to have a common and well-understood PID policy across communities." - [R27] Page 15

¹⁷"...different sets of policies are enforced to varying degrees, and sometimes the identifiers are not resolvable (e.g., IUPAC InChI-KEY...)" - [R27] Page 15

¹⁸"...each semantic artefact... must have sufficient associated documentation... Any semantic artefact should also be FAIR." - [R27] Page 17

¹⁹"There should be a clear EOSC PID policy, accommodating any appropriate PID usage..." - [R27] Page 16

²⁰ [R42] in the sheet 'Aspects'

		standards, or structural formats?	
Format Fragmentation in Research Data	Integration Tools for Bridging Formats	Does the repository use services or tools which are also available to translate, transform, mediate between different data formats (e.g. package structures, file formats, metadata standards)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishes URI to service or documentation for a transformation service if such service is available • Publishes the tools used for this service • Publishes if the service or tool is part of a workflow, such as ingestion, validations)

3.2 Semantic Interoperability

The aim of Semantic Interoperability is to ensure that the meaning of the preserved data and metadata is interpreted consistently across Information Systems and communities. This means that every time data is shared with a different Information System or community, it must contain the required meaning so that the receiving Information System or community can interpret it, even if it contains algorithms or vocabulary which are unknown for the receiving Information System or community. This requires that the correct data, including its meaning, must be exchanged.

Just storing data and metadata is not enough for digital preservation and curation. Future systems and researchers must still be able to interpret the information exactly as intended at the moment of creation. In addition, the efficient reuse, reproduction, and collation of data requires precision, which in turn can be improved considerably through use of semantic artefacts: PIDs, vocabularies, and ontologies. Implementation of these artefacts across the research enterprise not only improves research processes, but also simplifies attribution and rating of outputs, reporting, and knowledge base creation. Achieving this requires unambiguous definitions of terms of concepts, data elements and metadata fields, linked to persistent identifiers, and preserving the semantic artefacts, identifier registries. Equally important is comprehensive documentation of the digital object, capturing its context, structure and provenance. This ensures its meaning remains clear even as technologies evolve and community practices change. For research data to be usable across disciplines, there must be an alignment between community metadata standards and vocabularies, supported by reliable crosswalks that enable a mutual understanding.

Because the meaning of terms must itself be preserved, semantic artifacts such as ontologies, taxonomies, code lists and schemas must follow the FAIR principles²¹. Embedding FAIR-compliant semantic artifact management into preservation workflows guarantees that meaning is retained alongside the content.

While it might seem appealing and efficient to define a single common metadata model for all communities, the diversity of scientific disciplines, their specialised vocabularies and their rapid evolution make such a model both impractical and potentially reductive. Instead, EDEN is focusing on metadata crosswalking, dereferencing artefacts by the use of persistent identifiers and maintaining FAIR semantic artefact repositories with open licensing, versioning and governance.

By prioritising translation, dereferencing and FAIR governance over defining one schema which has to be adopted in a variety of disciplines, EDEN safeguards semantic richness while enabling interoperability. This approach supports both seamless cross-system data exchange today and the enduring interpretability required for preservation at scale.

²¹ <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/recipes/introduction/brief-FAIR-principles.html#fcb-fair-principles>

Semantic interoperability is context-dependent, and the standards, vocabularies, and schemas that enable it are typically agreed by research domains and communities, and may be further refined and specialised for institutional, network, or research infrastructure federation. Many domains already publish and promote best practice recommendations, and an option for ensuring its completeness can be found in [FAIR Implementation Profile](#)²² templates.

Based on the requirements and recommendations described in the Interoperability Framework of EOSC being the main reference material, internal sources from the EOSC EDEN, such as the Core Preservation Processes [R26] (EOSC EDEN WP1) and the Discipline-Specific Requirements [R6] (EOSC EDEN WP3) also were taken into account and four considerations were identified:

1 Lack of Metadata Harmonisation Across Domains: Use of shared metadata profiles, standards, and/or controlled vocabularies is a key to interpret data across different domains and communities by both humans and machines[R27].

Aspects derived from the consideration are:

- Support for domain-specific metadata profiles²³
- Crosswalks between metadata schemas²⁴
- Multilingual metadata support²⁵
- [Schema.org](#) or FAIR-compliant metadata exposure²⁶
- Reference repositories for semantic artefacts^{27,28,29}

2 Inconsistent Use of Controlled Vocabularies and Ontologies: Lack of consistency between repositories and communities in the use of controlled vocabularies and ontologies to describe the metadata fields. There are a wide variety to describe terms of use, missing identifiers and/or non-aligned semantic frameworks that hinder semantic clarity and cross-domain understanding and thereby machine interoperability of metadata [R27].

Aspects derived from the considerations are:

- Use of community-endorsed controlled vocabularies³⁰
- Machine-readable vocabulary linking³¹
- Vocabulary harmonisation and mapping services³²

²² <https://www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/fair-implementation-profile/>

²³ "There should be extensibility options to allow for disciplinary metadata... allowing users/researchers to add annotations according to the established practices of their communities..." - [R27] Page 18

²⁴ "A set of alignments (also known as crosswalks) among existing metadata models should be maintained..." - [R27] Page 17

²⁵ While not mentioned explicitly, multilingual support is indirectly implied by the need for broad accessibility and harmonisation across international communities.

²⁶ "A minimum metadata model should be proposed... based on reuse of existing standards like DCAT-AP, DDI 4 Core, DataCite core schema..." [R27] Page 17

²⁷ "The previous problem is exacerbated by the fact that there is a generalised lack of common reference repositories or registries of semantic..." [R27] Page 16

²⁸ "EOSC should provide support for the maintenance of a repository of semantic artefacts, and a governance framework for such a repository" [R27] Page 17

²⁹ "Every semantic artefact that is being ... of usage and conceptual diagrams. Furthermore, any semantic artefact should also be FAIR" [R27] Page 17

³⁰ "All communities should generate clear and precise definitions for the concepts that they use, as well as their metadata and data schemas." - [R27] Page 17

³¹ "Every semantic artefact that is being maintained in ... semantic artefact should also be FAIR." - [R27] Page 17

³² "...a set of alignments (also known as crosswalks) among existing metadata models should be maintained..." - [R27] Page 17

- Support for multilingual vocabularies³³

3 Lack of Persistent, Resolvable Identifiers for Semantic Entities: Semantic reasoning, automated linking and deduplication between systems will be unreliable when these elements are not represented by globally unique and resolvable identifiers [R27].

Aspects derived from the consideration are:

- Use of PIDs for semantic terms³⁴
- Support for semantic identifier dereferencing³⁵
- Alignment with recognised identifier systems³⁶

4 Fragmentation of Semantic Annotation Practices: The differences between the annotation of semantic metadata across systems could reduce the consistency and reusability of semantic information [R27].

Aspects derived from the consideration are:

- Support for embedded semantic annotations³⁷
- External annotation services or tools³⁸

In Table 3.2.1, three informative example aspects connected to semantic interoperability are listed. A list of all the identified aspects can be found in Appendix C or in the spreadsheet³⁹.

Table 3.2.1: Semantic Interoperability Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Identified attributes
Lack of Metadata Harmonisation Across Domains	Support for domain-specific metadata profiles	Does the TDR or TDA have the capability to expose metadata that is following community- or discipline-specific metadata profiles in addition to generic standards?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the default metadata profile which is used? • Does the system let users select a metadata profile? • Is the metadata validated against its profile? • Does the system give references to the documentation of each profile? • The system is giving a URL, on which the schema can be found machine-readable • Are there any crosswalks available and from and to the metadata schemas? • Does the system register its profile to a community registry? • Support extension of profiles?
Inconsistent Use of Controlled Vocabularies and Ontologies	Machine-readable vocabulary linking	Whether the system has the capability to expose the controlled vocabularies and ontologies terms in such	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishes a list of machine-readable formats it is supporting • Publishes URIs which resolve to a useful representation of terms

³³ While not explicitly stated, multilingualism is implied in the need for vocabularies to be “FAIR” and “shared across disciplines

³⁴ “All communities should generate clear and precise definitions for the concepts that they use... These definitions should be publicly available, referenced by a persistent identifier...” - [R27] Page 17

³⁵ “Every semantic artefact... must have sufficient associated documentation... Furthermore, any semantic artefact should also be FAIR.” - [R27] Page 17

³⁶ “Semantic artefacts should be available preferably using open licenses (e.g., like in W3C)... EOSC should provide support for the maintenance of a repository of semantic artefacts...” - [R27] Page 17

³⁷ “There should be extensibility options to allow for disciplinary metadata... with sufficient provenance information on the annotations, and with versioning support.” - [R27] Page 18

³⁸ “Need for principled approaches and tools for ontology and metadata schema creation, maintenance, governance and use.” - [R27] Page 17

³⁹ [R42] in the sheet ‘Aspects’

		format it is machine-readable which increases metadata interpretation, reasoning and integration across systems automatically.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which well-known namespaces are used in the metadata • URI or reference to documentation for the vocabulary of use • API which offers an endpoint to query or explore linked vocabularies
Lack of Persistent, Resolvable Identifiers for Semantic Entities	Alignment with recognised identifier systems	Whether the system is aligned with well-established identifier systems for common metadata entities, which increases the discoverability and reuse.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indicates which established PID systems are supported and used • URI to the system policy for PIDs types and formats

3.3 Organisational Interoperability

Aside from technical and semantic alignment between actors and systems in the research life cycle, digital preservation and access services, there should also be operational cohesion across the diverse organisations, service providers and user communities. This ensures a seamless and sustainable user experience for researchers, regardless of institutional affiliation or disciplinary background. However, Organisational Interoperability is not limited to making it more convenient for the users. At an organisational level, it requires clear governance structures, alignment of business processes and shared responsibilities so that services are trustworthy, sustainable and consistently accessible across borders and disciplines.⁴⁰

Organisational Interoperability considers the capacity of different organisations to align policies, governance structures, roles and operational workflows towards mutually agreed objectives. For EDEN, these objectives include safeguarding accessibility, integrity and usability of preserved digital objects for decades to come.

An important aspect of Organisational Interoperability is establishing clear governance. The first iteration will focus on cross-walking organisational roles and responsibilities for preservation, curation and access services, while ensuring that metadata catalogues, PID registries and preservation workflows have clear ownership and long-term maintenance commitments [R27].

Preservation workflows often involve multiple service providers, such as data deposit, format migration, integrity checks. To minimise friction for researchers moving data through different parts of the preservation ecosystem, these services must be coordinated and compatible with each other. This deliverable will therefore also aim to define mechanisms for assessing whether services meet agreed organisational and technical standards, thereby strengthening the users' trust.

Organisational Interoperability is not an isolated layer. It underpins the technical and semantic layers. Without agreed organisational processes, technical integrations risk fragmentation and metadata standards may be inconsistently applied. With a strong organisational alignment, EDEN can assure that preservation metadata, storage policies and access controls remain consistent over decades, safeguarding interoperability.

Organisational Interoperability focuses on the capacity of different organisations to align their business processes, responsibilities, and expectations. This type of interoperability is essential to ensure that services are not only technically and semantically integrated, but also operational coherent from an organisational perspective. The focus of this layer is aligning institutional policies, roles, and service workflows. This is important especially when multiple service providers are working together to deliver consistent experiences

⁴⁰ "According to the EIF, organisational interoperability refers to the way in which organisations align their business processes, responsibilities and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals." - [R27] Page 12

to users. This also includes making sure that services are user-focused, documentation is clear, and easily accessible so that there is little to no friction for researchers to achieve their goals.

Based on the requirements and recommendations described in the Interoperability Framework of EOSC being the main reference material, internal sources from the EOSC EDEN, such as the Core Preservation Processes [R26] (EOSC EDEN WP1) and the Discipline-Specific Requirements [R6] (EOSC EDEN WP3) also were taken into account and five considerations were identified:

1 Misalignment of Institutional Policies: When participating organisations operate under differing internal regulations, strategic priorities, or operational norms. These divergences may affect how data is curated, accessed, shared, and preserved, thereby creating friction in cross-institutional collaboration [R27].

Aspects derived from the consideration are:

- Repository has a publicly accessible data policy webpage⁴¹
- Policy includes machine-readable terms⁴²
- Policy includes versioning information⁴³

2 Inconsistent Service Workflows: Inconsistent or undefined service workflows across organisations hinder Organisational Interoperability by creating fragmentation in how services operate and interact. This is particularly evident in processes such as data deposit, onboarding, or metadata handling, which often vary between providers. The lack of clear terms, conditions, and acceptable use policies, combined with insufficient guidance in participation rules, results in misalignment of responsibilities and expectations across communities.

To address this, workflows such as data publication must be standardised. Data providers should be explicitly required to publish data according to agreed formats and vocabularies relevant to their specific communities. Standardised workflows across providers are essential for building trust, ensuring operational consistency, and enabling seamless collaboration across the ecosystem [R27].

Aspects derived from the consideration are:

- Standardised data deposit process⁴⁴

3 Undefined Roles and Responsibilities: The lack of clearly defined roles and responsibilities presents a critical barrier to effective collaboration and service integration within EOSC. When ownership of services is undefined or undocumented, it leads to confusion around accountability, maintenance, and long-term sustainability. This impairs coordination between service providers and diminishes trust among users relying on those services [R27].

Aspects derived from the consideration are:

- Published service ownership⁴⁵

⁴¹ "Need for documents explaining terms and conditions and acceptable use policies for services providing interoperability." - [R27] Page 19

⁴² Not explicitly stated, but FAIR implies machine-actionable metadata and terms

⁴³ "User rights, restrictions and conditions of use may change over time... right-statements made in the past may no longer reflect the current rights-holder..." - [R27] Page 19

⁴⁴ "The current set of rules ... specific data formats and/or vocabularies for a specific community." - [R27] Page 19

⁴⁵ "It should also be clear who is responsible for ... common interoperability services like service catalogues, registers and common PID services." - [R27] Page 19

- Role metadata in deposit and curation⁴⁶

4 Lack of User-Centric Service Design: When services aren't designed with users in mind, it becomes harder for researchers to use tools and systems from different organisations. These services can be confusing, inconsistent, and hard to access, especially for researchers working across different platforms or fields. In terms of Organisational Interoperability, this means systems may be difficult to find, understand, or use without help or experience. This can make collaboration and access to shared resources much more difficult.

Aspects derived from the consideration are:

- Accessibility and support documentation⁴⁷

5 Federated Identity and Trust Frameworks: Does the service participate in a federated identity infrastructure that allows researchers to authenticate using their home institutions or trusted external identity providers? Federated identity and trust frameworks are critical for enabling secure and seamless access across different organisations, infrastructures, and services within EOSC. They require formal agreements, policy alignment, and technical integration with identity federations, ensuring that user credentials and roles are trusted and recognised across domains.

Aspects derived from this consideration are:

- Federated identity support⁴⁸

Table 3.3.1 shows three informative example aspects connected to Organisational Interoperability. A list of all the identified aspects can be found in Appendix C or in the spreadsheet⁴⁹.

Table 3.3.1: Organisational Interoperability Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Identified attributes
Inconsistent Service Workflows	Standardised Data Deposit Process	Whether the system supports a harmonised, community-aligned workflow for data publication and deposit. This includes ensuring that data providers follow agreed protocols for metadata generation, format selection, validation, and submission. The standardisation of deposit workflows fosters interoperability, simplifies reuse, and ensures consistent metadata quality across domains.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whether the system enforces the use of community-agreed metadata standards during deposit • Whether there is a defined sequence of steps for data publication • Whether data deposits are linked to persistent identifiers and versioned consistently • Whether machine-actionable APIs are available to support automated or assisted deposit processes
Undefined Roles and Responsibilities	Published Service Ownership	Whether the system provides publicly available information on the ownership, custodianship, or stewardship of services and components. This	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whether service ownership is clearly documented and published.

⁴⁶ Not explicitly mentioned but, "Most research communities are already accounting for the need to align to the overall goals for Open Science that EOSC is looking for... lack of recognition for this additional work, both from institutions and colleagues." states that there is a lack of recognition, which identifies a need for standardization in roles - [R27] Page 12

⁴⁷ "Clear descriptions of... service-level agreements... providing catalogues and registries of semantic artefacts..." - [R27] Page 19

⁴⁸ "Need for a clear governance framework that includes clear instructions on how the other levels ... (data formats, AAI services, metadata schemas, ontologies, etc.). This should also include the management of permanent organisation names and functions" - [R27] Page 18, 19

⁴⁹ [R42] in the sheets 'Aspects'

		includes identifying the responsible individuals or entities for service operation, maintenance, and decision-making, which enhances transparency and accountability within EOSC.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whether the owning organisation or contact point is persistently identified. • Whether changes in service ownership are tracked and versioned over time. • Whether ownership metadata is exposed through service catalogues or registries.
Lack of User-Centric Service Design	Accessibility and Support Documentation	Whether the system provides clear, user-friendly pathways for users to access, understand, and effectively use its services, particularly in cross-disciplinary or multi-platform research environments. This includes the availability of comprehensive documentation, tutorials, help interfaces, and support services that lower the barrier to entry and promote effective onboarding. Accessibility also refers to the clarity of service offerings, consistency in interfaces, and ease of locating and using relevant resources.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whether the system provides structured, up-to-date user documentation and tutorials. • Whether multilingual or discipline-specific help resources are available. • Whether user support services are integrated and accessible.

3.4 Legal Interoperability

EDEN is not only focusing on combining datasets under compatible licenses, it is equally concerned with preserving the legal context alongside the data. In digital preservation, conditions such as copyright expiry, evolving privacy laws and shifting licence regimes must be tracked over time. Metadata should therefore carry time-stamped, machine-readable legal status information so that future reusers can determine legality decades later.

A factor, common across all interoperability layers, is the ability for automation without the need of human intervention[R27]. Legal conditions must be clearly stated, compatible and where possible automatically interpreted by machines.^{50, 51} For EDEN, this means embedding licence metadata in machine-readable format such as RDFa⁵² and/or JSON-LD⁵³, enabling harvesting tools to assess compatibility. It also requires using standardised vocabularies for rights such as ODRL⁵⁴ or Create Common Rights Expression Language⁵⁵, so preservation systems can automatically flag incompatible combinations before integration.

One even would argue that EDEN is not just about a preservation infrastructure but a compliance preservation infrastructure, where legal, ethical and regulatory contexts are curated alongside the data so that future reuse is legally sound without repeating the original legal due diligence.

Legal Interoperability focuses on the ability to access, combine, and reuse data and services in a way that is compliant with applicable laws, policies, and conditions of use. This is to ensure that the exchange and reuse of research outputs can happen legally and responsibly across different institutions, jurisdictions, and domains. This type of interoperability is essential to support the FAIR principles, particularly reusability, within

⁵⁰ "the legal use conditions are clear and readily ... , typically through automated means;" [R40] Page 1

⁵¹ "The use of standardised electronics ... comprehensibility by a wide audience– including by machines." [R40] Page 5

⁵² <https://rdfa.info/>

⁵³ <https://json-ld.org/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>

⁵⁵ <https://opensource.creativecommons.org/ccrel/>

EOSC EDEN. It ensures that services are not only technically and semantically aligned, but also legally usable from a rights and compliance perspective.

The focus of this layer is on making sure that the legal conditions governing data use are clearly stated, compatible, and, where possible, automatically understandable by machines. This is important especially when multiple datasets or services are used together, each carrying their own licenses or regulatory restrictions. Legal Interoperability addresses challenges such as combining data with different Creative Commons licenses, dealing with privacy laws like GDPR⁵⁶, or working within national access restrictions for sensitive data.

This also includes ensuring that data usage conditions are transparent and standardised, metadata remains FAIR even when data access is limited, and that users do not face unnecessary legal barriers to reuse. It requires that documentation of access conditions is consistent, rights information is clearly defined, and any constraints are communicated in ways that can be processed automatically and understood across systems.

Legal Interoperability enables researchers and service providers to operate with confidence, knowing that reuse is legally sound, scalable, and respectful of ethical and regulatory boundaries.

Some of the considerations identified in this section on Legal Interoperability may have direct overlap with issues discussed in section 5 on Rights & Ethics of this deliverable. To avoid duplication, the task will consolidate these overlaps towards the second iteration, ensuring consistency across the two sections while keeping interoperability concerns explicitly visible.⁵⁷

Based on the requirements and recommendations described in the EOSC Interoperability Framework the main reference), internal sources from the EOSC EDEN, such as the Core Preservation Processes [R26] (EOSC EDEN WP1) and the Discipline-Specific Requirements [R6] (EOSC EDEN WP3) five considerations were identified:

1 Issues related to Licence Compatibility and Reusability: Datasets are often reused, recombined or republished in different institutional or national boundaries. However, they could differ in terms of licence even among open licenses. It could create conflict that makes reusability and interoperability impossible. Ensuring that licenses which are applied to datasets, metadata and services are compatible for combination and reuse, and that users can determine its reusability without legal knowledge [R27].

Aspects derived from this consideration are:

- Licence alignment and combination of licences^{58, 59}
- Use of standardised open licenses⁶⁰

2 Lack of Clarity and Automation of Legal Conditions: Ensuring that terms which data can be accessed and reused are clearly defined and machine-actionable. Data needs to be not only legally shareable, but licence terms must be automatically understood by software systems [R27].

⁵⁶ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

⁵⁷ This overlap does not create redundancy but instead ensure alignment across different perspectives. The final consolidation will harmonise the considerations under Rights & Ethics with their interoperability implications.

⁵⁸ "Legal interoperability requires... that data should be reusable. It concerns the ability to combine datasets from multiple sources without conflicts among restrictions imposed by the license of each dataset." - [R27] Page 12

⁵⁹ "Restrictions can inhibit reuse to a greater extent than is sometimes realised" - [R40] Page 8

⁶⁰ "The fewest restrictions contained in the source datasets will result in the fewest restrictions contained in the combined or derivative datasets." - [R27] Page 13

Aspects derived from this consideration are:

- Machine-readable licensing terms^{61,62}
- Metadata describing access and use conditions^{63,64}

3 Restriction Handling and Compliance: Scientific research data often contains sensitive information, such as personal data, health records, or protected species locations⁶⁵ that cannot always be shared openly. Legal rules like GDPR, national security laws, or ethical policies may limit how data can be accessed or reused. To support responsible sharing and reuse, research repositories must clearly show what restrictions apply to the data, and where needed, apply technical protections like embargoes (delaying access), redacting sensitive parts, or generalising data.

Researchers need to understand these restrictions easily, and machines should be able to read them too, so data can still be discovered, cited, and used within legal and ethical limits [R27].

Aspects derived from the consideration are:

- Embargos, redaction, and generalisation mechanisms^{66,67,68}
- Documentation of applicable restrictions^{69,70}

4 Restrictions on Policy and Regulatory Alignment: When researchers share or reuse data across countries, institutions, or disciplines, they may face legal or policy restrictions, for example due to GDPR, national laws, or repository-specific rules. These restrictions can limit access, sharing, or even publishing of datasets. To make data truly reusable and interoperable, it's important that repositories and services clearly align their access and usage policies with national and EU-level regulations. This helps researchers understand what they can legally do with the data, without needing to be legal experts [R27].

Aspects derived from the consideration are:

- Alignment with EU and national data policies^{71,72}

⁶¹ "Legal interoperability requires that metadata is FAIR... and that the conditions for access and use are clearly and readily determinable through automated means and that they do not conflict with each other." - [R27] Page 13

⁶² "The use of standardised electronic statements regarding the legal rights retained (if any) by the rights holders and providers of research data can greatly assist in their comprehensibility by a wide audience—including by machines." - [R40] Page 5

⁶³ "In cases where access to data is restricted or subject to conditions, legal interoperability requires that metadata is FAIR... enabling data discovery, that the conditions for access and use are clearly and readily determinable." - [R27] Page 13

⁶⁴ "The metadata for any publicly available collection of data therefore should include all information ... that are both human and machine readable" - [R40] Page 20

⁶⁵ "Protection of endangered species: Specific data and information referring to endangered species must, in certain circumstances, be withheld in the interest of their protection." - [R40] Page 17

⁶⁶ "A number of mechanisms are used in practice to restrict access to data where such regulatory or policy measures exist e.g., embargo, data redaction, data generalisation..." - [R27] Page 13

⁶⁷ "Where personal privacy protection or confidentiality interests require withholding of certain data, an evaluation should determine whether sharing can be assured by making such data available in anonymised or aggregated form." - [R40] Page 18

⁶⁸ "Time embargos on the release of research data may be justified by scientific needs... However, such restrictions should be narrowly limited in time and be specified by the funder of the research" - [R40] Page 19

⁶⁹ "Legal interoperability also concerns situations where regulatory or policy measures restrict the disclosure of data... e.g., based on intellectual property law, national security, protection of endangered species or privacy regulations, such as GDPR." - [R27] Page 13

⁷⁰ "The metadata for any publicly available collection of data therefore should include all information ... that are both human and machine readable" - [R40] Page 20

⁷¹ "There are a number of 'enabling' legal instruments... EU directives and regulations, national laws, EU and national policies... that support legal interoperability." - [R27] Page 13

⁷² "Governments and organizations engaged in the research process can facilitate legal interoperability using compatible and consistent terms and conditions for research data rights across as many jurisdictions as possible. Possible mechanisms for achieving such harmonization include treaties, legislation, public policy, common-use licenses, and waivers of rights" - [R40] Page 22

- Evaluation of licence mandates at different levels⁷³

5 FAIR Metadata Despite Restrictions to Data Access: In scientific research, some datasets cannot be openly shared due to legal, ethical, or privacy reasons, for example, because of GDPR, national security, or sensitive human data. However, even if the data itself cannot be accessed, it is still important that the metadata describing the data remains FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) [R27].

Aspects derived from the consideration are:

- Use of persistent identifiers for restricted data⁷⁴
- Publishing of access policies even for restricted content^{75,76}

In Table 3.4.1 are three informative aspects connected to Legal Interoperability. A list of all the identified aspects can be found in Appendix C or in the spreadsheet⁷⁷.

Table 3.4.1: Legal Interoperability Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Identified attributes
Clarity and Automation of Legal Conditions	Metadata describing access and use conditions	Access rights and usage conditions for data should be clearly expressed in metadata to inform users and enable automated decision-making.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata includes access condition fields • Standard terms or controlled vocabularies used • URI pointing to detailed access policy
Restriction Handling and Compliance	Documentation of applicable restrictions	Systems should publish documentation explaining the legal or ethical restrictions applied to datasets, ensuring transparency for end users and systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • URI to restriction policy or legal guidance • Metadata includes justification for restriction • Indicates responsible authority for applying the restriction
FAIR Metadata Despite Restrictions	Publishing of access policies even for restricted content	Repositories should expose access policies for restricted datasets in a machine-readable way so that users and automated systems can understand access limitations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access policies are publicly available • Machine-readable access policy formats supported • URI to access condition documentation

3.5 Challenges of Archival Information Packages

In the OAIS Information Model, which is part of the OAIS Reference Model [R32], Archival Information Packages (AIPs) are internal packages that are held and managed within an archive. This is shown in Figure 3.5.1 below.

⁷³ "There is a need to examine whether obligations or recommendations to use certain licenses, in particular at the national level, are coherent with specific recommendations that are or may be adopted by the EOSC interoperability framework." - [R27] Page 13

⁷⁴ "FAIR data does not necessarily mean Open... In cases where access to data is restricted... metadata is FAIR, i.e., using accepted standards to describe the data and thereby enabling their discovery." - [R27] Page 13

⁷⁵ "FAIR principles do not restrict recognition of legitimate reasons for shielding data... conditions for access and use are clearly and readily determinable..." - [R27] Page 13

⁷⁶ "The metadata for any publicly available collection of data therefore should include all information—a rights statement—necessary to understand the legal control of the data and any terms and conditions governing their access and reuse... Legal interoperability—even for data that may have some additional restrictions—thus can be significantly enhanced by means of a common taxonomy in rights statements that are both human and machine readable." - [R40] Page 20

⁷⁷ [R42] in the sheet 'Aspects'

Figure 3.5.1: OAIS Model. Reproduced from the OAIS specification [R32]

AIPs are a critical part of the OAIS Information Model and digital preservation because they are intended to contain not just digital objects, but all the information needed in order to preserve and provide access to those digital objects in the future. This includes the structure and semantics of the digital objects plus information on their identifiers, context, fixity, provenance, and rights.

Whilst AIPs are primarily internal to an archive, there are several important scenarios where AIPs need to be externalised from an archive and exchanged with other TDAs and digital preservation environments. Scenarios include: transfer of AIPs when custody and responsibility for their care is transferred between TDAs; replication across multiple TDAs or services as part of business continuity and disaster recovery; and the ability to send AIPs in whole or in part to third-party preservation services for storage or so that preservation actions can be applied. A summary of these scenarios is in [Appendix H: Scenarios for AIP Interoperability and Exchange](#) and further analysis is provided in [Annex to D2.1: EOSC EDEN AIP Services](#)⁷⁸

3.5.1 Considerations and Aspects of AIP Interoperability and Exchange

The main challenge with AIP interoperability and exchange is a lack of common approaches and standards across TDAs (Please see [Annex to D2.1: EOSC EDEN AIP Services](#)). Furthermore, attempting to enforce or mandate a single standardised approach is highly likely to fail due to the very wide range of data formats, standards and specifications that are used for the various components of an AIP, several of which can be discipline-specific such as descriptive metadata, data structures and file formats.

In Table 3.5.1.1 are the considerations identified for AIP interoperability and exchange.

⁷⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17183330>

Table 3.5.1.1: AIP Considerations: Inventory

Consideration	Description	EOSC Interoperability Framework Level
Lack of well defined semantics for AIPs	Organisations use a wide range of formats, standards, schemas, vocabularies and ontologies for their holdings, many of which can be discipline-specific. There is no consistent way for organisations to describe the semantics of their AIPs.	Semantic
Diverse range of formats and specifications used for AIPs	Organisations use a wide range of formats, specifications and structures for their data and metadata. There is no consistent way for organisations to describe the technical details of their AIPs, for example when they are exchanged.	Technical
Lack consistent approach to implementing the OAIS Information Model for AIPs	OAIS is one of the defacto standards for AIPs. However, OAIS is a logical Information Model and implementation is left up to the TDA that decides to follow it. This results in inconsistent or varied approaches and a difficulty in assessing AIPs against the OAIS Information Model.	Technical
Lack of well defined mechanism for exchanging AIPs between organisations and systems	There is not a well defined protocol and API for exchanging AIPs between TDAs, including where AIPs can use a range of standards and formats for their contents and may have multiple versions that evolve over time.	Technical
Lack of consistent Machine-readable rights for the Digital Preservation of AIPs	A TDA must have the legal basis for retaining AIP contents and applying preservation actions so that the contents remain usable over time. This includes any rights needed to enable AIPs to be transferred to third-parties, e.g. other TDAs or external preservation services.	Legal

These considerations lead to a set of aspects that need to be addressed. Two examples are placed in table 3.5.1.2. Further aspects are in the table in [Appendix C: Design Considerations](#).

Table 3.5.1.2: AIP Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Attributes
Lack of well defined semantics for AIPs	Evaluation of AIPs against the semantics of the OAIS Information Model	A TDA should be able to describe each component of its AIPs in terms of the OAIS Information Model so that the AIP can be evaluated for completeness and conformance to the OAIS Information Model. For example, which component of the AIP corresponds to PDI, Representation Information, Data Objects etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The TDA can map each component of its AIPs to a corresponding entity in the OAIS Information Model
Diverse range of formats and specifications used for AIPs	The technical details of each component of an AIP are well defined and at all levels.	There needs to be a mechanism that allows a TDA to describe each component of its AIPs in terms of the technical formats, specifications and standards that are used. For example, the formats used for metadata (e.g. JSON, CSV, XML etc), references to the schemas that apply (e.g. DataCite, DCAT etc.), the specifications used for layout (e.g. OCFL), the information package standards followed (e.g. E-ARK), the technical mapping to the OAIS Information Model, and how content is packaged for transfer (e.g. Bagit).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The TDA can describe the technical standards and specifications it follows for all aspects of serialising and packaging an AIP.

3.5.2 Services and Requirements for AIP Interoperability and Exchange

In EDEN, work on AIPs is focussed on AIP services for interoperability and exchange. The proposed approach is to use OAIS Packaging Information to describe the contents of an AIP according to the OAIS Information Model. This leads to the need for services for both describing packages and validating the contents of such packages w.r.t the OAIS Information Model. When an AIP has been described using OAIS Packaging Information and is serialised and validated, then it is ready for exchange. This requires an exchange service.

A detailed analysis of the expressiveness of the OAIS Information Model for AIPs and whether it is able to accommodate the wide range of AIP content types that need to be supported in EDEN is provided in [Annex to D2.1: EOSC EDEN AIP Services](#). Considerable effort could be spent creating a comprehensive set of requirements for an EDEN AIP specification, for example listing every type of information that needs to be stored in an AIP or listing every preservation process that can result in artefacts that need to be recorded in an AIP such as provenance metadata, file formats, checksums and so on. However, given the work that has already gone into existing AIP specifications, for example E-ARK, the OAIS Reference Model (OAIS RM) and the OAIS Interoperability Framework (OAIS IF), are likely to already be sufficient. Furthermore, EDEN should re-use and build upon existing standards where possible and avoid re-inventing the wheel. Therefore, the approach we have taken to detailed requirements analysis for EDEN AIPs (see the Annex) is to determine whether existing standards can be reused for EDEN, either as-is or with further extensions. The conclusions of this analysis are:

- The information in EDEN AIPs can be described by the OAIS Information Model.
- There are no significant gaps in the OAIS Information Model that prevent it from describing EDEN AIPs.
- The full OAIS Information Model is both sufficient and necessary.

The above means that the OAIS Information Model for AIPs can be used to form the basis of Packaging Information for EDEN AIPs, and in turn, this can enable EDEN AIPs to be evaluated for OAIS conformance, and then exchanged between parties.

It is also important to state that EDEN does not mandate that the EDEN AIP specification is used within a TDA as part of its day to day operations. That isn't to say that a TDA shouldn't use the EDEN AIP specification internally if desired, and indeed it may be beneficial to do so, for example to help confirm that it does indeed have the information it needs in its AIPs in order to fulfil its remit. The main purpose of the EDEN AIP specification is for use when a TDA needs to demonstrate OAIS conformance and to exchange content with external parties. This could be when exchanging AIPs with another TDA; it could be exchanging AIPs with external digital preservation services; it could be when demonstrating to assessment and certification bodies that the TDA holds the necessary information in their AIPs to fulfil their duties; or it could be when the TDA is asked to demonstrate transparency and good practice to Producers or Consumers.

The set of services proposed in this section can be chained together to support an AIP exchange workflow. An example is shown below. For more information, please refer to the Annex to D2.1 on AIP Services.

Figure 3.5.2.1: Example AIP Exchange Workflow and Services

Many of the considerations and aspects in Table 3.5.1.2 and related aspects in [Appendix C: Design Considerations](#) can be satisfied by providing a mechanism for archives to describe the content and format of their AIPs when they are externalised and exchanged. In OAIS the ability to do this is provided by OAIS Packaging Information⁷⁹. The use of OAIS Packaging Information to describe the contents of an AIP leads to the need for two services, one for AIP Semantic Packaging Information and one for AIP Technical Packaging Information. These services are described below.

Table 3.5.2.1: AIP Describing services

Service	EOSC Interoperability Framework Level	Description
AIP Semantic Packaging Information Service	Semantic	The service allows a TDA to describe the contents of an AIP by providing OAIS Packaging Information for the AIP. The packaging information shall be able to describe the formats, schemas, vocabularies, standards and specifications that are used for all components of the AIP in order to ensure the semantics of each component are well defined.
AIP Technical Packaging Information Service	Technical	The service allows a TDA to describe the contents of an AIP by providing OAIS Packaging Information that describes the technical details of the AIP. This allows external entities to understand both the contents of the AIP and what standards and specifications are being used for the serialisation and exchange of the AIP.

⁷⁹ OAIS definition: “Packaging Information: The information that describes how the components of an Information Package are logically or physically bound together and how to identify and extract the components.”

The ability to fully describe the contents of an AIP in terms of the OAIS information model enables individual AIPs to be assessed for their level of conformance. This leads to the need for AIP services that can be used for validation and conformance testing:

Table 3.5.2.2: AIP Validating services

Service	EOSC Interoperability Framework Level	Description
AIP OAIS Semantic Validation Service	Semantic	The Packaging Information for an AIP is evaluated against the components of the OAIS Information Model to determine the extent to which some or all of the required components of OAIS are present in the AIP. This allows the level of OAIS conformance to be assessed according to the semantics of the OAIS Information Model.
AIP OAIS Technical Validation Service	Technical	The OAIS Packaging Information for an AIP is tested to validate the AIP contents at a technical level. This includes validation of the Packaging Information against a schema in order to check that it is syntactically valid, i.e. well-formed, and testing of the contents of the AIP to confirm they are present and correct as listed in the Packaging Information.
AIP Rights Validation Service	Legal	The TDA can check the rights statements in an AIP to confirm that it has a valid legal basis for holding the AIP, performing preservation actions on it, and/or transferring it to other TDA or using third-party preservation services.

Once AIPs are described and validated using OAIS Packaging Information then they can be exchanged with external entities such as other TDAs or external preservation services in the knowledge that the receiving party will have the information needed to be able to interpret and process the contents of the AIP. This leads to the need for an AIP exchange service:

Table 3.5.2.3: AIP Exchanging services

Service	EOSC Interoperability Framework Level	Description
AIP Exchange Service	Technical	It should be possible to request and transfer an AIP from one location to another, e.g. between TDAs. The service that supports AIP exchange should support incremental and full transfers (e.g. transfer of a whole AIP in one shot for small AIPs or transfer in batches of files for large AIPs).

The need to accommodate the wide range of formats, standards and specifications used for AIP contents will inevitably require services that can be used to convert AIP components between formats and specifications. This includes metadata cross-walks and package transformations such as repacking using a different structure or container. There are other services in EOSC that support this functionality such as the Metadata Schema Cross Walk Registry (MSCR) and they are not discussed further here.

4 Quality assurance of research outputs

The scope of quality assurance of research outputs is very wide, and many interpretations are possible, ranging from a focus on process quality (whether procedures and best practices are followed), to the fitness for use (content-focused) in a given application. The latter is obviously strongly context dependent (the nature of the research question being addressed, the discipline in which the research takes place, and so on), while the former is more general in nature. Figure 4.1 provides an attempt to represent the scope of process and content quality assessment of research outputs, together with levels of generalisation and formalisation.

Figure 4.1: Scope of Quality Assurance of Research Outputs

For the purposes of this specification, the focus will be quite strongly on those concerns that can be addressed by any repository by comparing the characteristics of a research output and/ or its provenance to standards and established best practices. It is useful for repositories to also make judgments on the applicability and usability of the content ('fitness for use'), but such actions are heavily dependent on human expertise and unlikely to be automated in the near future.

In the context of research outputs and research data, community expectations in respect of best practice, as formalised in sets of principles and criteria such as [FAIR](#) [13], [CARE](#) [14], and [TRUST](#) [15], are an important aspect of quality assurance performed by repositories⁸⁰. In some cases, these considerations are elaborated in much more detail (for example in the [CoreTrustSeal](#), [ISO 16363](#) and [Nestor](#) certification criteria and guidelines related to TRUST), or are extended to be more domain-specific (for example with FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIP) developed for specific communities).

⁸⁰ Such community expectations mostly precede the publication of e.g. FAIR and TRUST principles. We use it as a collective definition of groups of best practice.

4.1 Contextual Data Quality

Contextual data quality addresses aspects of quality that should be verified by curators on the basis of best practice and standards.

The objectives of such quality assurance is largely focused on authenticity and integrity of objects submitted for publication and archiving. Some of the considerations are purely technical, and are discussed in the section on Technical Data Quality, and some are discussed in the section on Metadata Quality. Several additional concerns deal with ethical research practices and the rights of stakeholders, and these are discussed in a separate chapter on Rights and Ethics. The remainder is focused on those considerations that deal with the following:

1. **Applicability and Alignment:** Curators need to determine whether content satisfies the acceptance criteria of the repository, and whether it aligns with the mandate and appraisal policies of the repository. These could be quite varied, and may be determined on the basis of domain, data type, data size, and sensitivity of the data. Defining repository attributes in this respect is quite important, because it contributes to the selection of the most appropriate repository by depositors.
2. **Completeness:** Is the set of deposited objects self-sufficient in respect of future use? At least some of these aspects can be assessed automatically, but the scope of such determinations are very wide.⁸¹ In addition, support documentation (readme files, data dictionaries, etc.) will improve reusability [R7].
3. **Intellectual Property and Ownership:** Curators have to be sure that the depositor represents the wishes of the intellectual property owners in respect of publication, in other words that the depositor has the right to publish or archive the object. In cases where there are a large number of authors, for example, obtaining such evidence is not a trivial exercise. At the minimum, a depositor could be asked to confirm that the consent of all contributors have been provided.
4. **Authenticity and Originality:** Content submitted to repositories need to be verified in respect of authenticity (it is what it claims to be), and originality (it is not a copy of materials already submitted elsewhere, has not been plagiarised, or has not been generated artificially). See below for a more detailed discussion of these aspects.
5. **Provenance Metadata:** Information about the creation of the object assists with determining its authenticity and integrity [R7], but is also a prerequisite for support of reproducibility in science.
6. **Legal and Contractual Aspects:** Illegal content needs to be detected and avoided, and depositors should honour the terms of use and any contractual obligations they have in respect of the content that is submitted. Sensitive data needs to be assessed in terms of the level of protection that should be implemented, and special attention should be paid to GDPR-related concerns [R7].
7. **Fitness for Use:** This aspect is significantly affected by context. Datasets that are useful for some applications in a specific domain may not be suitable for others (for example on the basis of precision or resolution), and some datasets are useful across multiple disciplines and for general policy and decision support, while others are not. See 'Data Readiness' (section 4.3.2).

For each of these considerations, curators need to determine whether the submitted objects meet with repository, community, and disciplinary expectations. As indicated in the introduction, such determinations can focus on either process-related aspects or on content-related aspects, or both. In addition, end users, certification authorities, and funders, amongst others, may require information on the extent to which a repository has implemented measures to address these considerations.

⁸¹ As an example - Some audiovisual files may have to include codecs as a dependency, and survey data files more often than not are not interpretable without a code book. Relational or graph databases require all relational and entity or node tables to be available, and spatial data files, depending on the format, are not complete without a minimum set of file components.

Authenticity and integrity, combined with legal and contractual obligations, present a special set of considerations in respect of the detection of fraudulent or inappropriate deposits. These following cases need to be identified and mitigated by a repository:

- **Malicious content** that is capable of damaging the computers of users and employees of archives.
- **Illegal content** that is prohibited under national and international legislation, including material that violates copyright.
- **Falsified content** intended to support particular interests that are contrary to the scientific consensus.
- **Nonsense content** that is likely to damage the scientific reputation of repositories.
- Content that otherwise **breaches the terms of use** of the repository.
- Content that has been **plagiarised**

One can evaluate fitness for use via the general 'readiness' of datasets and research outputs from a number of perspectives, using frameworks such as Data Readiness Framework DaReFF [R1]⁸². The framework covers many of the contextual quality-related considerations mentioned above. The framework could be extended as a mechanism for classifying and describing quality in general - refer to 'Methodology'.

Table 4.1.1 shows three informative examples of aspects connected to contextual data quality. A list of all the identified aspects can be found in Appendix C or in the spreadsheet⁸³.

Table 4.1.1: Contextual Data Quality: Inventory and Attribute Identification

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Identified attributes
Legal uncertainty	Legal clearance	The repository provides mechanisms and tools to assess the legal compliance of its assets.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Legal compliance indicated in metadata ● Legal (self) assessment tool available
Documentation gaps	Contract and consent management	The repository manages its users' contracts and consents and assigns them to individual digital objects as necessary such as preservation agreements etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Links to user related contracts and agreements available ● Contract and consent management system in place
Legal and Regulatory	Legal - GDPR Compliance	The repository verifies whether personal data is included in the deposit (including pseudonymised data), and if so, follows a procedure to determine the level of protection required and implements it.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Personal/ Sensitive Data Policy exists ● Privacy Statement available ● Personal Data Removal Request Procedure exists ● Confirmation of personal data removal can be provided ● GDPR-Compliant Privacy Statement is available

4.2 Metadata Quality

Metadata quality is an important factor in long-term data preservation and reuse. High-quality metadata ensures that archived datasets remain Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) over time.⁸⁴ The FAIR principles focus on rich, machine-readable metadata as the basis for discovery and reuse of digital objects. In practice, this means repositories must not only collect sufficient descriptive information, but should

⁸² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15186741>

⁸³ [R42] in the sheet 'Aspects'

⁸⁴ <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/recipes/introduction/metadata-fair.html>

also do so in a standardised, machine-actionable way aligned with community needs.⁸⁵ Poor metadata quality can cause even well-preserved data getting undiscoverable, thus unusable. While the lack of adequate metadata may cause that the data cannot be understood or reused.⁸⁶ Below, considerations for metadata quality in the preservation context are discussed, each linked to one or more aspects that repositories and curators should address.

1. **Metadata Completeness:** Curators must ensure that data objects are described by a minimal set of essential descriptive metadata. Core metadata fields should be present and filled out. Incomplete or minimal metadata reduces findability and understanding of the data. Repositories typically enforce some required fields at deposit, but completeness here goes beyond formal requirements – it involves providing rich context so that a potential user can grasp the what, who, when, where, and how of the data object.
2. **Metadata schema Compliance:** Metadata should conform to recognised schemas or community standards, using structured formats and consistent semantics. Adhering to standard metadata schemas improves interoperability between systems. Repositories should align with community metadata standards (FAIR principle R1.3) and document which schemas they support.
3. **Machine-Actionable Metadata:** Metadata must be not just human-readable, but should also be able to be processed by machines without human intervention. This means providing metadata in structured, parseable formats (e.g. XML, JSON-LD, RDF) and using globally unique, resolvable identifiers and vocabularies. The FAIR principles highlight machine-actionable metadata, especially I1 (formal languages) and A1/A1.1 (standard protocols). To support discovery of a repository's interoperability affordances, the FAIR Interoperability Catalogue - FAIRiCat⁸⁷ - approach can be used.
4. **Multilingual Metadata:** In a global and interdisciplinary research ecosystem, metadata may need to be understood by speakers of different languages. Providing multilingual metadata can greatly enhance the accessibility of data, allowing wider audiences to find and comprehend the resource.
5. **Metadata Fitness for Reuse:** Beyond basic description for discovery, good metadata should also convey the context, provenance, and other information needed to reuse the data in the future. Recording the provenance of the data (FAIR principle R1.2: metadata should include detailed provenance) and a clear usage licence is paramount here.
6. **Automated FAIR Metadata assessment:** A key aspect of metadata quality is how well the metadata scores against the FAIR principles. Metadata should not only serve local discovery and reuse needs, but also comply with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) to ensure that both humans and machines can locate, interpret, and act on the metadata over the long-term. Curators want to automate FAIR assessment of the deposited data. The FAIR assessment scores should be available from the repository, preferable on the object-, collection- and repository aggregated levels. Automated FAIR assessments are scalable and consistent. They will contribute to progress tracking and guidance for improvement over time.

Each of the above considerations contributes to overall metadata quality in a digital preservation setting. There are currently several initiatives dedicated to supporting these aspects: for instance, [FAIRsharing](https://fairsharing.org) offers a registry of data and metadata standards and databases, helping stakeholders identify appropriate standards for their data. The [FAIRassist](https://fairassist.org) portal aggregates tools and guidance to help improve metadata and data FAIRness. Furthermore, emerging frameworks like in the EU-project [OSTRAILS](https://ostrails.eu) are defining common FAIR assessment metrics and specifications, which include checks on metadata quality, but it also focuses on FAIR guidance in the broad sense, which includes guidance typology and focus areas amongst others.

⁸⁵ <https://fairsharing.org>

⁸⁶ The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship

⁸⁷ <https://signposting.org/FAIRiCat>

Table 4.2.1 shows three informative examples of aspects from different considerations related to metadata quality. A list of all the identified aspects can be found in Appendix C or in the spreadsheet⁸⁸.

Table 4.2.1: Metadata Quality: Inventory and Attribute Identification

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Identified attributes
Automated FAIR Metadata assessment	Aggregated FAIR assessment scores	The curator, or the system includes a FAIR score in the deposit and publishes them on different levels.	FAIR assessment aggregated scores available on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • object level • collection level • repository level
Metadata Fitness for Reuse	Usage license	Metadata holds sufficient context for reuse of the data, such as usage license.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata records include a data usage license statement from a license list
Machine-Actionable Metadata	Repository affordances discovery	Repository affordances, like an OAI-PMH endpoint, should be findable not only by humans, but also by machines.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repository compliance to the FAIRiCat89 specifications
Metadata schema Compliance	Metadata Standards Alignment	Metadata needs to conform to metadata standards or schemas relevant to the domain or general best practice. Repositories should declare which metadata schema(s) they use and support interoperability via mappings.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A repository publishes the metadata standards it uses. • Crosswalks or mappings to other schemas are available to support exchange. •

4.3 Technical Data Quality

Technical data quality refers to such properties of a research object (such as a dataset) that can be established and verified via automated or algorithmic methods. Such methods can be standardised, and can be provided by services. There are two main considerations for determining and evaluating such properties:

1. **Metadata Confirmation:** To enhance or otherwise supplement the scope of metadata and its accuracy (metadata completeness). As examples: a file may be presented as a given MIME type, but it is prudent to verify that the file is indeed such a type; spatial coverage can be accurately determined directly from file data, or one may want to compute the checksum of a file or collection of files for integrity management.
2. **Data Assessment:** Computing properties of the dataset to inform on aspects such as precision and variance, presence of outliers, or nature of the data distribution. Such (mostly statistical) properties can be used to identify possible errors and anomalies in the data. It can also assist with the identification of possibly fake or fraudulent data.

The properties determined by such methods can be assessed against expectations of some sort, expressed as benchmarks and optionally derived from standards. Examples of such assessments might be to compare file formats against preferred format guidance, or determine whether a spatial coverage is consistent with the expected coverage for such a dataset. It is clear that for many such properties, automation of the associated quality assurance processes will not be possible without the availability of machine-actionable benchmarks.

⁸⁸ [R42] in the sheet 'Aspects'

⁸⁹ Specifications for local encoding of repository attributes [R5]

Some of the technical properties of a research object (for example, the aspect ratio of an image or the spatial coverage of a dataset) are immutable and should be preserved during any transformation or improvement of such an object. These are referred to as **significant properties**⁹⁰. Extracting technical metadata from the digital objects is a process of documenting technical (incl. significant) properties. The majority of metadata schemas do not make explicit provision for the registration of file-level properties in detail. Such ‘file-level’ metadata can be varied, and only some of these properties are determined automatically.

Significant properties document technical aspects of files and file formats that are essential for the use, interpretation and understanding of digital content. These properties are aspects of files that are translated to how the files are rendered and how digital bytes convey information that is rendered meaningful for human interaction. Significant properties are often related to the type of file, for example text-based files use a character set to translate digital information to meaningful text, while image files typically have properties that define the dimensions of the image, its colour profile and bit depth.

A TDA must define which significant properties of files are, preferably for each file format it preserves, and how they are documented. Significant properties are essential when performing preservation actions such as file format migrations. With the aid of documented significant properties, it is possible to plan and evaluate a migration. By analyzing how the significant properties change from one file format to another, or using different tools in the process, the quality of the migration process and the impact it has on the content can be assessed. Significant properties are also needed when conducting file repair, i.e. fixing files with validation errors, in which the evaluation of how big of an impact a repair action has on the content is important.

Technical metadata is the documented, standardised form of the significant properties. Technical metadata should be extracted from the files using various tools and stored in standardised forms, such as PREMIS [R31], [NISO IMG](#)⁹¹ or [textMD](#)⁹². Standardised metadata fosters interoperability and aids in implementing tools for transforming or repairing files. By extracting metadata from files using tools, it is possible to create workflows for repairing or transforming files, that include automated quality control by comparing metadata before and after the process.

Overall, technical data quality relates to how a TDA manages file formats and aims to be domain agnostic, despite variations due to domain-specific formats that may require harmonisation. In order to enable digital preservation and mitigate risks to the content that are to be preserved, the TDA must have a process on how to handle file formats that are ingested. Digital preservation is about keeping digital information intact, authentic, and usable for a long time. Actions that enable keeping the data usable are file format management, file format migration and emulation. The strategy of migrating file formats is about preserving the content in file formats that are currently usable, transforming file formats that are at risk of becoming obsolete into formats that are viable. Emulation is rendering the files in specific environments, and it requires information about the hardware and software that is required to render the files.

Both strategies rely on a TDA to know in what formats the content is preserved and that the data is in a quality that does not effectively hinder these strategies. The TDA should be able to identify the file formats in its holdings, to identify the technical characteristics and to validate the file formats when ingesting content. The purpose of file format validation is to ensure that the data can be properly migrated and validated in the future, i.e. that any errors in the files do not block these strategies, and that the files can be rendered or processed with documented tools.

⁹⁰ The term ‘significant property’, which has various definitions in the literature, is sometimes used in a way that is consistent with it being a Transformational Information Property. See [32].

⁹¹ https://www.loc.gov/standards/mix/docs/NISODataDictionary_March2002.doc

⁹² <https://www.loc.gov/standards/textMD/>

File format migration typically requires a TDA to specify a set of file formats that can be preserved and used by the documented tools. The TDA must utilise a process for appraising file formats that are suitable for preservation and provide support for file format normalisation for file formats that are not suitable for digital preservation.

Table 4.3.1 shows three informative examples of aspects related to technical data quality considerations. A list of all the identified aspects can be found in Appendix C or in the spreadsheet⁹³.

Table 4.3.1: Technical Data Quality Aspects: Inventory and Attribute Identification

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Identified attributes
Files are not in a supported or sustainable file format	Format normalisation	Files in unsupported formats are normalised to formats that are sustainable and sustainable for digital preservation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Files are in sustainable formats. The service provides guidance for high-quality format conversions.
A repository does not have information on how to repair an invalid file	File format validation error database	The TDA should document commonly encountered file format validation errors and their solutions in a regularly maintained database.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Repository maintains a database that documents file format validation errors. Repository has defined a process for updating the database.
Files have not been evaluated for format appraisal (i.e. how suitable is the file format for digital preservation)	File format appraisal	File formats must have been evaluated for appraisal, indicating how suitable they are for preservation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evidence of how suitable different file formats are for preservation.

93 [R42] in the sheet 'Aspects'

5 Rights & Ethics

The subject of rights and ethics, viewed from a repository perspective, covers considerations relating to the motivations for, and sources of, rights and ethics management, existing policies and guidelines that make recommendations or provide best practices in respect of such management, and the tension that exists between the objective of Open Science ('as open as possible, as closed as necessary'), and the rights of many actors involved in the life cycle of research outputs. The landscape is further characterised by a diversity of approaches to management of rights and ethics evident in software platforms for repositories and registries, repository implementations based on that software, and aggregations of research outputs. An additional challenge arises from the lack of widespread standardisation of licence encodings and vocabulary to describe such encodings. Moreover, many licences are custom-made for a specific application, and for widely-used licences, there is limited support for the unambiguous and persistent referencing of these licences.

For this review, an analysis is made of the main design considerations and detailed aspects of these considerations, with a view to contextualising the implications it has for services (services offered to, or implemented by, repositories to ensure quality in respect of rights and ethics management), the repository attributes that record, prove, or advertise the capabilities and actions taken by repositories in this respect, and the requirements and specifications associated with the services that we identified. The EOSC Interoperability Framework considers the management of rights and licences to relate to **Legal Interoperability** concerns [R27], and WP1 in the EOSC EDEN project has identified rights and access management in two of its Core Preservation Processes [R26]. Some of the considerations identified in this section may have direct overlap with those identified in the section on Legal Interoperability of this deliverable. To avoid duplication, the task will consolidate these overlaps during the second iteration, ensuring consistency across the two sections while keeping interoperability concerns explicitly visible.

The community expectations listed by FAIR [R14], CARE [R13], and TRUST [R15] in general, and elaborated for example by trustworthy repository certification authorities in some cases, deal with a variety of considerations - the need for transparent and standardised licences and access conditions, verification of ethics clearance, maintenance of subject rights and confidentiality of sensitive data, etc.

5.1 Copyright & Law

The following four considerations apply:

1. **Legal and Regulatory:** The protection of personal and private data is a legal requirement in many countries, and in the EU, national GDPR legislation [R21] and Digital Services Act [40] are the main considerations here. These are often extended by regulations and legal obligations that are domain- or context-specific, for example having to destroy anonymised medical records after a period of time. Commercial and legal information is generally confidential, with such confidentiality legally protected. It is also a common requirement in research situations that involve sensitive data (social sciences, humanities, life sciences, environmental sciences, law and commerce) that institutional ethics clearance is a requirement prior to commencement of the research.
2. **International Agreements and Frameworks:** These also sometimes impose regulatory obligations on repositories, for example adherence may be required to the [Nagoya Protocol](#) [R23].
3. **Balancing Rights and Openness:** The objectives of Open Science include the notion that resource outputs be as open as possible, and as closed as necessary. This objective is sometimes viewed as being at odds with the rights of subjects associated with a research object [R28]. Depending on how transparently the provisions for safeguarding rights are formulated, this is not necessarily true: what should be avoided is the practice of non-transparent, arbitrary access conditions.
4. **Sovereignty:** There is a recent growth in emphasis on data sovereignty [R29] that is in conflict with the objectives of Open Science, since it may lead to situations where reuse of resources is limited on the

basis of location or nationality. At the minimum, it may require proof of physical location of storage and the locus of control.

Table 5.1.1 shows three informative examples of aspects related to copyright and law considerations. A list of all the identified aspects can be found in Appendix C or in the spreadsheet⁹⁴.

Table 5.1.1: Copyright & Law Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Identified attributes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal uncertainty 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal clearance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The repository provides mechanisms and tools to assess the legal compliance of its assets. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal compliance indicated in metadata Legal (self) assessment tool available
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documentation gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contract and consent management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The repository manages its users' contracts and consents and assigns them to individual digital objects as necessary such as preservation agreements etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Links to user related contracts and agreements available Contract and consent management system in place
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal and Regulatory 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal - GDPR Compliance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The repository verifies whether personal data is included in the deposit (including pseudonymised data), and if so, follows a procedure to determine the level of protection required and implements it 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal/ Sensitive Data Policy exists Privacy Statement available Personal Data Removal Request Procedure exists Confirmation of personal data removal can be provided GDPR-Compliant Privacy Statement is available

5.2 Licensing and Digital Rights Management

There is a clear need for standardisation and convergence of licences [R28] - not only open or 'free culture' licenses, but also licences that manage access with a view to the protection of subject interests or sovereignty concerns. The landscape for digital rights management is not harmonised, though, and characterised by diversity:

- **Clarity:** Clear statements of rights and information about legal conditions are necessary to give users the assurance that the reuse of data and digital objects is possible and permitted, and under what conditions this may be done.
- **Licence Identification:** Lack of a universally-adopted service that uniquely identifies and persistently resolves the definition of a licence, although services such as [SPDX](#) and [DALICC](#) achieve this in part.
- **Licence Encoding:** the provisions included in licences are also not harmonised, with various options for implementation available to end users and systems developers, including [ODRL](#) [R11], [DALICC](#), [ccREL](#), and [REL/MPEG-21](#). Some harmonisation of the vocabulary describing these provisions is under way in the EOSC Beyond Project, with an availability in September 2025.
- **Focus on Owner(s):** If one recognises the fact that current licence provisions and licence expressions are almost universally focused on the owner(s) of the rights to the work, and not the subjects of

⁹⁴ [R42] in the sheet 'Aspects'

research in the case of works that are outputs of a research activity, or the end users and managers of resources and services (repositories, aggregators), it is not surprising that restrictions and obligations in respect of the subjects described in the work are poorly developed.

- **Machine Readability:** In several software platforms, it is possible to record access conditions and restrictions as free text, and as such, it is quite difficult to index and / or expose these limitations to end users in a consistent way, let alone automate non-human tasks in the access request process.
- **Licence Compatibility:** Most works are derivations of multiple input resources (code, data, etc.), each of which can have a different licence. Many licences require derivatives to maintain the provisions of the original work, and as such, this could lead to incompatibilities in the licence choice for the output. The problem has partly been addressed by the [DALICC project](#).
- **Granularity:** The general applicability of a licence, as described here, is at the level of a 'work' (a dataset, code repository, publication). There are at least two cases of implementation of licence-like provisions at finer granularity:
 - In the case of datasets or code, it is common for these objects to be composites of files or bitstreams, and it may be required to apply different licences to the individual files rather than the composite object.
 - Licences are composites of licence provisions (e.g. permissions and obligations). Some communities implement granular application of ad-hoc combinations of provisions to an object - resulting in a custom 'licence' for each object.
- **Re-appraisal:** there is a need to re-evaluate appropriateness of licences periodically [R30], [R31] for a variety of reasons, including:
 - It could be triggered by changes in legislation or regulations.
 - Copyright or embargoes may have lapsed.
 - Legacy deposits may be misaligned with current legislation.
- **Access Rights and Licences:** The OAIS RM [R32] regards licences as a subset of 'Access Rights Information', but in practice, it is convenient to include all permissions, restrictions, duties or obligations, and other limitations in machine-readable format in a licence, since this information is then not repository-dependent or arbitrary, and always available in a defined manner [R33].
- **Custom and Specialised Licences:** there is a widespread practice of creating custom licences and access conditions, and in some cases, such access conditions contradict the provisions of a licence selected for a resource [R33].

The considerations discussed above apply to digital objects that are archived and disseminated by repositories. A distinction should be made between management of rights and licensing of metadata, and the object described by the metadata:

- **Metadata:** Is generally licensed under an explicit public domain licence (e.g. CC0) or is implicitly in the public domain [R34].
- **Sensitive Metadata:** Some elements in a metadata record may be sensitive⁹⁵. Access to metadata records cannot be restricted completely, since this renders the resource undiscoverable and unable to be cited. A simple mechanism to place sensitive metadata in an access-controlled file in a dataset can be implemented in most repository software systems [R35].
- **Bibliographic Data:** GDPR applies to all personal data, including the particulars of authors and contributors to a work. Such data is typically not managed under GDPR, and citations and metadata are freely exchanged, harvested, and copied in the normal course of research activity [R36]. The

⁹⁵ Such as the location of observations of endangered species, or the identity of holocaust survivor interviewees.

motivation for excluding bibliographic data from GDPR provisions and its scope should be noted in a privacy statement, for which guidance on formulation is available [R20].

Table 5.2.1 shows three informative examples of aspects related to licensing and digital rights management considerations. A list of all the identified aspects can be found in Appendix C or in the spreadsheet⁹⁶.

Table 5.2.1: Licensing and Digital Rights Management Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Identified attributes
Licensing conflicts	License standardisation	The repository uses commonly accepted machine-readable standard terms (or URIs) to indicate licenses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata standards supporting explicit indication of licenses • Standard vocabulary used for licenses • Machine-readable licenses
Licensing conflicts	License guidance	The repository provides user guidance to select the most appropriate license	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • License selection tool available
Licensing conflicts	Licence provision	The repository maintains a registry or list of accepted licenses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licence registry or dictionary available

5.3 Policy Considerations

A significant focus of rights and ethics management in repositories and archives is the implementation of policies and procedures that ensure compliance or alignment with specific objectives. The policies and procedures, defined widely here to include contractual arrangements between actors and guidance aimed at improved alignment, can be characterised as follows:

- **Clear Policies:** Policies should provide clear and transparent information on general conditions and rules that apply to the use of individual services or objects and associated duties and responsibilities. However, they are usually unstructured, apply at different levels of granularity, are provided in written form, and sometimes contain information that is difficult to understand or is contradictory.
- **Characteristics of Policies and Procedures:** Policies must be 'reproducible' and transparently available, be revised with appropriate frequency, and meet minimum conditions for well-structured policy or procedure documents [R8] (e.g. actors and responsibilities clearly defined). Policies can be encoded and responsibilities assigned to actors, and ODRL [R11] provides a blueprint for linking policy provisions to licence provisions.
- **Policy Groups:** The most commonly referenced policies were determined from a sample of re3data entries, and collated with the typical evidence of policies, procedures, and user support documentation expected from repositories by certification authorities and the TRUST principles. Not all these have direct links to rights and ethics considerations, but it is also not uncommon for such documents to offer guidance or define policy in respect of rights and ethics.
- **Vocabulary:** These policy groups, and evidence that repositories have them available, should ideally be referenced via a standard vocabulary. PREMIS [R31], DRAWG, and Dublin Core vocabularies provide limited terms for such referencing, and will be inadequate as a means of describing all evidence required by certification authorities in a consistent and machine-readable way. In addition, the [Data Use Ontology \(DUO\)](#) [R12] and the recent publication of a [Data Privacy Vocabulary \(DPV\)](#) [R10] enables encoding of some policy provisions and privacy statements in machine-actionable formats.

⁹⁶ [R42] in the sheet 'Aspects'

- **Frequency of Use:** It is clear from the analysis of the sample of re3data entries that there is a wide variation in the frequency of references to policy documents in an illustrative sample of repositories (Figure 5.3.1).
- **Profiles:** Given that a definitive list of policy, contractual, and user support documentation can be defined, the extent to which repositories develop and expose evidence of such documentation is context-dependent, determined by the aims of the repository and its certification ambitions (or not). This indicates the need to be able to define profiles of attributes, and such profiles can have multiple purposes: A checklist of requirements from a certification authority, an inventory of terms defined by a controlled vocabulary, and so on.

Frequency of Occurrence: Policy Groups (n=500)

Figure 5.3.1. Frequency of Occurrence of Policy Groups

The scope of the policies, guidelines, licences, and legal documentation and obligations that are covered here apply to multiple actors, and this is an important consideration when writing and implementing policies, procedures, and licences - responsibilities have to be clearly defined and assigned to specific actors [R28], and ODRL compliance requires such actors to have [unambiguous IRIs](#) [R11]. At present, such IRIs are only partially supplied by widely used schemas (e.g. [DCAT](#), [schema.org](#), [ODRL](#) [R11]), and a need exists for unambiguous definition.

Table 5.3.1 shows three informative examples of aspects related to policy considerations. A list of all the identified aspects can be found in Appendix C or in the spreadsheet⁹⁷.

⁹⁷ [R42] in the sheet 'Aspects'

Table 5.3.1: Policy Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Identified attributes
Inconsistent policies	Policy standardisation	The repository exposes policies in a standardised way.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata standards supporting explicit indication of policies
Inconsistent policies	Policy (type) provision	The repository uses a controlled vocabulary to indicate the policy type of its policy documents.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy vocabulary used • Policy documents indicate policy type in metadata
Policy and Regulatory Alignment	Inventory	Repositories should make a list of applicable policies available in a machine-readable way	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy inventory list with links to latest copies

5.4 Contract / Preservation Agreement

Contractual obligations of actors should be fully documented, including both digital copies of contracts and online form entries. All contractual documents and agreements must be stored securely, and those relating to each actor must be made available to them in a transparent manner.

Table 5.4.1 shows three informative examples of aspects connected to contract/ preservation agreement considerations. A list of all the identified aspects can be found in appendix C or in the spreadsheet⁹⁸.

Table 5.4.1: Contract/ Preservation Agreement Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Identified attributes
Transparency of Access and Rights	Transparency	Repositories ensure that all access conditions, restrictions, or limitations are transparent, and preferably machine readable.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Machine-actionable licences used • Provisions are encoded using a published vocabulary
Authenticity and Originality	Research Origin Verified	The repository verifies that the submission was made by a researcher or someone making a deposit in a research context, and that it is a dataset associated with original research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depositor context verified • maDMP is available and linked • Peer-reviewed publication linked
Documentation gaps	Contract and consent management	The repository manages its users' contracts and consents and assigns them to individual digital objects as necessary such as preservation agreements etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Links to user related contracts and agreements available • Contract and consent management system in place

⁹⁸ [R42] in the sheet 'Aspects'

5.5 Ethics Considerations

Ethical research practices include emphasis on the rights of the subjects of research, and to some extent on the manner in which sensitive data will be dealt with. It overlaps with legal considerations in respect of personal data and privacy, which is discussed earlier. Institutions, domains⁹⁹, networks¹⁰⁰, and projects¹⁰¹ often provide context-specific regulations or policies. Moreover, deviations from ethical standards that fall below the threshold of illegal action must also be prevented by means of appropriate countermeasures. In broad terms, the following considerations apply:

- **Interests of the Subjects:** Research institutions usually require confirmation from a researcher or project that the interests of the subjects of study will be dealt with in an ethical manner. The scope of sensitive data related to subjects, and their interests, cover a wide scope - including personal identifiable information, sensitive ecosystems, experiments on live animals, the concerns and cultural, natural, or social assets of indigenous communities¹⁰², and legally/ commercially privileged information. The CARE Principles [R13] are specifically focused on indigenous peoples' rights, interests, and wellbeing at all stages of the data life cycle, and CODATA has published high-level recommendations in this respect [R17]. The European Commission provides a checklist for identification of sensitive data risks [R37].
- **Unethical Research Practice:** Institutional policies and best practices often identify and proscribe plagiarism, violation of licence conditions of input resources, falsification of results, and other unlawful or unethical behaviour [40]. Generally, regulations and guidance require lawful activity [R22], [R24].
- **Guidance and Standardisation Resources:** There is a significant body of knowledge¹⁰³ in respect of guidance for researchers on ethical practices, and these often expressly identify measures applicable to research outputs (e.g. datasets). It may be relevant for repository selection to understand the repository's alignment with such practices and standards, and generally useful to researchers to have access to a structured body of knowledge. Values and principles applicable to repositories and libraries have been developed [R19], and could serve as an organising principle for guidance.
- **Evidence of Compliance:** It is good practice for object metadata to reference or link to ethics clearance documentation, consent documents, and in the case of HE-funded projects, to the required project self-assessment documentation. The exact terms to which participants have consented can be included by depositing or linking to a blank consent form as data documentation.
- **Authorship and Contributions:** These should be properly acknowledged, with a clear protocol on determining authorship and contributions, preferably by way of a standard 'Author Contribution Statement' accompanying the final published research output [26].
- **Citation and Attribution:** It is important for repositories to promote proper citation and attribution [26], [R28].

Table 5.5.1 shows three informative example aspects related to ethics considerations. A list of all the identified aspects can be found in appendix C or in the spreadsheet¹⁰⁴.

⁹⁹ For example the Nagoya Protocol [R23].

¹⁰⁰ For example the EOSC Rules of Participation [R39].

¹⁰¹ For Horizon Europe funded projects, Article 17 of the Rules of Participation deals with ethics regulations [R22].

¹⁰² As exemplified by the [CARE principles](#) [R13].

¹⁰³ [R9], [R13], [R16], [R17], [R18], [R19]

¹⁰⁴ [R42] in the sheet 'Aspects'

Table 5.5.1: Ethics Considerations: Inventory and Attribute Identification

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Identified attributes
Ethics Considerations	Fraud	The repository takes precautions to detect and reject fraudulent submissions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical integrity verification • Plagiarism check performed • Duplicate publication verified
Ethics Considerations	Inappropriate Content	The repository takes measures to identify and reflect inappropriate content.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Checked for malicious content • Checked for nonsense or irrelevant content
Ethical Constraints	Ethics governance	The repository has mechanisms in place to report on ethical misconduct and has a contingency plan in place.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feedback mechanism implemented

6 Services

The identification of the preservation and curation services to be developed in the EDEN project, followed a multi-step methodology to ensure the services defined address the actual needs of the community. The task began with gathering information from multiple sources, both internal and external. From this material, the task participants defined a set of considerations and aspects, which represent high-level problems or opportunities. Aside high-level problems or opportunities, they also covered principles such as FAIR, TRUST and CARE, legal and regulatory obligations, policy frameworks, and infrastructural and best practices, which could then be broken down into more detailed and related issues.

For each aspect, the task proposed service(s), including a description and references to examples of existing services or tools that could already provide (or contribute) to the solution. All services were documented in a structured spreadsheet, which includes additional information such as mapping to Core Preservation Processes (CPPs)[R26], links to relevant code repositories and supporting documentation.

Once the initial list was compiled, the members started discussing and reviewing each aspect if it was sufficiently addressed or remained unresolved. This assessment considered the maturity of existing services and tools, and whether a simplified interface or aggregator service would be required to combine information from multiple different sources, to create a one-stop service for clients.

The outcome of this process was a curated list of services. Only those services identified as candidates for further development are presented in this deliverable, in order to focus the requirements analysis and high-level specification work on the areas where EDEN can make the most impact.

Aside from the service inventory, effort also has been put in defining the information a service has to publish about itself and supportive vocabulary to describe it. This effort resulted in vocabulary for TRL (Technical Readiness Level) and properties which are necessary to describe a service which can be found in Appendix B.

For demonstration purposes, three examples of these services are presented in Table 6.1. A comprehensive list of identified services can be found in the spreadsheet¹⁰⁵.

¹⁰⁵ [R42] in the sheet 'Services'

Table 6.1: Examples of Relevant Services

Aspect	Services & Tools		Description
	Existing	Proposed	
Metadata Alignment across Heterogeneous Formats	<p>Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Name: FAIRsharing <p>Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - None 	EOSC Registry for supported schemas and crosswalks by the archive	<p>A lightweight add-on service that complements metadata archives by publishing and maintaining a curated list of supported metadata schemas, data formats, and crosswalks. The registry provides a lookup function so users can quickly see which schemas an archive supports, what crosswalks (mappings) exist between schemas and how metadata standards vary across disciplines.</p> <p>The service must be easy to integrate with archives and registries, enabling them to expose their schema and crosswalk support in a consistent, discoverable way. By offering this shared lookup layer, the registry lowers barriers for data providers, helps researchers choose the right repository, and facilitates interoperability across scientific communities.</p>
Technical metadata extraction	<p>Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - None <p>Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Name: Mediainfo, ExifTool, FFmpeg, File Scraper, ImageMagick, LibTIFF 	EOSC Metadata Extraction Service	<p>The service for extracting metadata from files produces technical metadata in a standardised interoperable format. Technical metadata is used for identifying significant properties of files, which can be used to plan and assess file format transformations and file repair actions. As file's properties are different for different types of files, technical metadata standards tend to focus on specific types of files. For example NISOIMG (MIX) is applicable for image files, while audioMD is meant for audio files and streams.</p> <p>Technical metadata is extracted using several tools, as one tool cannot cover the extraction of all properties for a diverse set of file formats. The metadata extraction service must include tools that can extract the relevant technical metadata for all file formats supported by the TDA. The metadata extraction service harmonises the output from the used tools and maps it to one or more technical metadata standards. Finally, the extracted metadata is serialised using the selected standard(s).</p>
License alignment and combinability	<p>Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - None <p>Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - None 	Licence Guidance Service	A system that provides licence guidance based on parameters.

7 Attributes

Attributes are descriptive properties, used to characterise services and aspects. They provide the mechanism for characterisation of services, repositories, and archives and assess suitability of these resources for a specific use case.

The identification of the attributes was done through a structured process that combined document reviews, expert consultations and iterative refinement. The process ensured that the attributes defined are comprehensive enough for discovery yet practical for implementation.

The first iteration focus has been deliberately set on identifying and structuring the attributes rather than comparing or aligning them with existing sources. A comprehensive list of all attributes captured from various sources is currently in creation and is not yet available¹⁰⁶. This means that the attribute set presented should be considered a baseline inventory. Future interactions of the work will refine, map and validate these attributes and make sure EDEN does not pre-empt developments in related initiatives, but ensures that proper alignment can be achieved when stable outputs are published.

Aside from identifying attributes, EDEN also tried to define the cardinality of the attributes. The cardinality indicates the number of values it can hold in relation to the service or repository. The role of the attributes is to serve as vocabulary for comparing, classifying and evaluating services and repositories. These attributes will support:

- **Discovery and filtering:** Enabling users to search and refine results based on attribute values.
- **Interoperability:** Ensuring alignment across communities by using common descriptors.
- **Assessment and monitoring:** Forming the basis for evaluating maturity, compliance, or suitability of services and repositories.
- **Registry and management support:** Attributes are particularly valuable for registries and managers, as they enable systematic selection of services according to specific needs. For example, a manager can filter services by “Target User,” “Domain of Use,” or “Supported Standards,” ensuring that the selected service best matches the requirements of their organisation or community.

We will develop guidelines for the implementation of specifications for exposing and sharing attributes in future iterations, taking recently published work by FAIR-IMPACT into account [R38].

For demonstration purposes, example attributes are presented in Table 7.1. A list of all the identified services can be found in Appendix A or in the spreadsheet¹⁰⁷.

Table 7.1: Attributes

Consideration	Aspect	Description
Aggregated FAIR assessment score on repository level	FAIR assessment aggregated score	The curator, or the system includes a FAIR score in the deposit and publishes them on different levels.
Machine-readable API documentation available	Reference implementations and API guidelines	Does the repository provide manuals or documentation for their services and protocols they use?
Defines access policy	Policy (type) provision	The repository uses a controlled vocabulary to indicate the policy type of its policy documents.

¹⁰⁶ Alignment with the work being done in the RDA TRSP WG serves as an example.

¹⁰⁷ [R42] in the sheet ‘Attributes’

8 Requirements

Task 2.1 in EOSC EDEN collected and analysed requirements derived from three primary sources: the work done in WP2 (largely focused on the expert inputs of team members in respect of technical design considerations), WP1 (the perspective of TDAs), and WP3 (expectations of domain-specific user communities). This process resulted in a large collection of requirements, consolidated in a dedicated spreadsheet¹⁰⁸. Additional sources we considered include, among others, the EOSC Interoperability Framework and the FAIR principles. Future refinements are expected, based inter alia on the TTRAM framework from the EOSC FIDELIS project [R44], and repository attribute definitions being finalised by the RDA TRSP WG.

The most mature analysis of requirements presented in this report is based on EOSC EDEN inputs. These include discipline-specific user requirements derived from Work Package 3 [R6] and the Core Preservation Processes [R26] developed in Work Package 1. Both provided valuable input from which further requirements were either adopted or derived. Since requirements originated from multiple sources, the task made an effort to combine, disambiguate, and consolidate them. In parallel, we connected them to external references wherever possible, thereby strengthening their relevance and applicability.

Based on the design considerations and associated aspects identified, often building upon the same underlying sources, we defined services to address the needs of both the CPP Framework and the discipline-specific user expectations. In the process of defining high-level specifications for these services, we identified the requirements applicable to each one. This process allowed us to connect the requirements with the services they support, ensuring coherence and traceability.

Table 8.1 presents a subset example of the requirements linked to the services that were identified as candidates for development. A more comprehensive list of all requirements can be found in the requirements spreadsheet¹⁰⁹, while the mapping of additional requirements to services is available in the services spreadsheet¹¹⁰.

Each row in Table 8.1 corresponds to a single requirement, and the columns have the following meaning:

- **Requirement ID:** A unique identifier, which contains the domain (interoperability, quality or legal), the type or section it belongs to (technical, legal etc.), and its sequential number. These IDs are persistent through the project EDENs duration for traceability across documents, spreadsheets, kanban boards and appendices.
- **Description:** A plain-language statement of the requirement.
- **CPP:** The mapping to which CPP (Core Preservation Process) it is relevant to. This makes it possible to track which requirements must be fulfilled in order to fit the process defined by WP1.
- **Priority:** Priorities shown are indicative; the final assessment of priority will be refined as the task will receive community feedback and requirements are getting more mature towards the second iteration.

¹⁰⁸ [R41] in the sheet 'Requirements'

¹⁰⁹ [R41] in the sheet 'Requirements'

¹¹⁰ [R42] in the sheet 'Services'

Table 8.1. Example Requirements

Requirement ID	Description	CPP	Priority
INTEROPERABILITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-001	The Trusted Digital Archive (TDA) must validate the checksums of received content against the checksums provided in the corresponding Information Package to ensure data integrity during and after transfer.	CPP-002_Checksum_Validation	Major - Mandatory
QUALITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-006	File formats must be documented.	CPP-008_File_Format_Identification	Major - Mandatory
QUALITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-010	File formats selected for preservation must not be protected by technical mechanisms in ways that prevent digital preservation actions.		Major - Mandatory
QUALITY-TECHNICAL-REQ-053	File formats selected as archival masters should have a lossless storage of data.		Minor - Optional
DISCIPLINE-SPECIFIC-REQ-027	As a researcher I need to know the history of improvements, edits and versions and I need information on versions of a dataset.	CPP-02_AIP_Versioning	Major - Mandatory

9 Specifications

The last step in the process is to create specifications for the curation and preservation services that Task 2.1 identified. Contributors prioritised services on their organisation’s needs, the maturity of the services description (for example CPP and requirements mapping), and based on what is feasible with the resources available for the task. This approach is a first attempt at identification of services that will be specified and developed. The list of priority services is likely to be refined and amended, prior to commencement of development and implementation. The specifications themselves were documented in the W3C specification format. This specification format gives a clear and standardised way to communicate both normative elements (in scope for determining specification compliance) and informative ones (guidelines and examples to assist with implementation).

In addition to specifications for a specific service, more generic, cross-cutting specifications will also be required. Examples include:

- Legal obligations (e.g. accessibility and privacy compliance from a service and systems perspective).
- Standardised API implementation (e.g. REST, GraphQL, and SPARQL).
- Exposure of repository and service attributes, based on community guidelines [R38].
- Minimum level of documentation (e.g. specification about human and machine-readable documentation for services, which have impact on most of the services in respect of interoperability).

The specifications will be used as a starting point for the development of selected services. For EDEN WP3 the services that were identified for implementation are important, since it will have an impact on the pilot methodology or testing strategy. They also set a baseline for the future iterations. The specifications will evolve due to community feedback, and adjustments to priority will be made based on needs of the community.

Table 9.1 presents a subset of the specifications written to serve as examples. The specifications contain a name, service which it relates to, if not a generic specification, and a high-level description based on what is written in the W3C specification. The W3C specifications will be published as supplementary materials when they reach a stable state. An overview of all the currently defined specifications, including their mapped requirements, can be found in the spreadsheet¹¹¹.

¹¹¹ [R41] in the sheet ‘Specifications’

Table 9.1 Example Specifications

Name	Service	High-Level description
Generic Authentication & Authorization Specification	EOSC License Compatibility & Guidance Service	This specification ensures that EOSC EDEN services adopt secure, standards-based, and federated authentication and authorization mechanisms. It guarantees that users and services can securely authenticate once and access multiple EOSC EDEN services, while authorization rules remain consistent and transparent.
Interoperability AIP Packaging Information Specification	AIP Semantic Packaging Information Service, AIP Rights Validation Service, AIP Exchange Service, AIP Technical Packaging Information Service, AIP OAIS Technical Validation Service	This specification is for a human and machine-readable format for Open Archival Information Systems (OAIS) Packaging Information for AIPs.
License Facade Service Specification	EOSC License Compatibility & Guidance Service	The specification covers the design and operation of a Licence Facade Service (LFS), enabling end users and developers to unambiguously identify and reference licences for datasets, and optionally obtain human- and machine-readable representations of the licence provisions where available.
Trusted Digital Archives (TDA): Interoperability, Documentation, Conformance, Capability Statements, and Verification Specification		This specification defines discovery, declaration, documentation, and automated verification requirements for Trusted Digital Archives (TDAs). It ensures TDAs expose interoperable machine interfaces for metadata and content exchange (e.g., OAI-PMH, OGC CSW, SPARQL), declare their properties in a uniform way, provide documentation and conformance testing evidence, and align with EOSC EDEN and CodeMeta service metadata schema.

10 Conclusions and Recommendations

The first iteration of the EOSC EDEN specification and architecture has established a solid foundation for a structured inventory of services in scope for digital preservation and curation, where further iteration can be built upon. By identifying design considerations and ideal practices, and recognising challenges and problems in achieving them, it was possible to derive important repository attributes, define services, inventorise the service requirements and write high-level specifications.

The analysis carried out has also highlighted the persistent challenges across all layers of interoperability. Technically, repositories continue to face difficulties with aspects such as format fragmentation, inconsistent APIs, adoption of several different persistent identifiers, and exposure and documentation of repository attributes. Semantically, as diversity will always exist across communities and disciplines in terms of metadata models and vocabularies, a standard mechanism which can describe the differences and is able to deal with it will probably improve the cross-domain interpretation by creating for e.g. an authoritative registry of metadata schemas. Organisationally, varying policies, workflows and ownership structures introduce friction between service providers, while legally, uncertainties around licensing, right and compliance with GDPR, and other regulations remain barriers to seamless reuse. These findings reinforce the importance of addressing not only technical specifications but also governance, trust and technical considerations in building a sustainable ecosystem.

At the same time, the deliverable underscores that quality and reusability are multidimensional. Preserved content must be accompanied by contextual data, metadata, and technical quality assurances that are consistent with FAIR, TRUST and CARE principles. Rights and Ethics cannot be treated as a separate concern, instead, they must be embedded in every part of repository services, from license metadata and embargo management to ethical review and accountability systems.

Looking forward, several priorities emerge. The inventory of repository attributes should, when in a stable state, be validated against widely adopted registries, and aligned where possible to enable greater transparency, comparability and discovery across infrastructures. A clear and simple mechanism for encoding, exposing and sharing these repository attributes must be provided. The service specifications drafted provide an essential starting point, but they must be refined through pilot implementations, testing and feedback from the broader community, and the same applies to prioritisation of the services. Ensuring that these specifications are made available in stable, machine-readable formats will further support adoption and can possibly be achieved by using FAIRCORE4EOSC CAT¹¹². In parallel, investment in shared standards, conformance testing tools and reference implementations will help overcome technical fragmentation.

Equally important is the need to strengthen legal and ethical interoperability, through common vocabularies for licenses, machine-actionable access conditions, and GDPR-compliant mechanisms for sensitive data. Cross-community collaboration should be fostered by federated discovery services, PDI harmonisation and alignment with the EOSC Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure. Finally, continuous engagement with the research community and coordination with or reuse of outputs from other EOSC initiatives such as EOSC Beyond¹¹³ and FIDELIS¹¹⁴ will be critical to ensure that specifications remain relevant, interoperable, and

¹¹² <https://github.com/FC4E-CAT>

¹¹³ <https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/>

¹¹⁴ <https://eosc.eu/horizon-europe-projects/fidelis/>

widely supported, while also keeping them aligned with finished initiatives such as FAIR-IMPACT¹¹⁵, FAIRCORE4EOSC¹¹⁶.

In conclusion, this deliverable contributes to the path towards the development of services for a sustainable and trusted data preservation infrastructure for European research. Building on established standards, addressing interoperability challenges, and committing to interactive refinement with the community will be essential as EOSC EDEN evolves to support reliable, ethical and scalable access to research outputs.

¹¹⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/>

¹¹⁶ <https://faircore4eosoc.eu/>

11 References

No	Description/ Link
R1	Puglisi, G., Bailo, D., Peters-von Gehlen, K., Bumberger, J., Steenbeek, J., Lange, O., Bonforte, A., Sieck, K., Cervone, L., Krijger, T., Sanchez Macias, J. L., Thiemann, H., Benincasa, F., Garavelli, S., Hof, C., Clea Lumina, D., Endresen, D., & Hugo, W. (2025). A Framework for Data Readiness (DaReFF) (1.0). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15186741
R2	Wikipedia (2025), Technology Readiness Level, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technology_readiness_level
R3	European Commission (2014). Technology readiness levels (TRL); Extract from Part 19 - Commission Decision C(2014) 4995, https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf
R4	Jones, M.B., Boettiger, C., Mayes, A.C., Smith, A., Gruenpeter, M., Lorentz, V., Morrell, T., Garijo, D., Slaughter, P., Niemeyer, K., Gil, Y., Fenner, M., Nowak, K., Hahnel, M., Coy, L., Allen, A., Crosas, M., Sands, A., Hong, N.C., Cruse, P., Katz, D.S., Goble, C., Mecum, B., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., & Ross, N. (2023). CodeMeta: an exchange schema for software metadata. Version 3.0. https://raw.githubusercontent.com/codemeta/codemeta/3.0/codemeta.jsonld
R5	Van de Sompel, H., Huber, R., Hochstenbach, P., Nelson, M. L., Klein, M., Bollini, A., Meijers, E., Knoth, P., Walk, P., Hugo, W., & Meyers, J. (2024). FAIRiCat: Supporting discovery of a repository's interoperability affordances. Signposting the Scholarly Web. https://signposting.org/FAIRiCat/
R6	Andreassen, H. N., Flügel, A.-L., Klemetsen, T., Smart, K., Benauer, M., Cannizzaro, G., Ciesla, M., Conzett, P., Huber, R., Høier, S., Laik, A., Lammert, A., Le Meur, J.-Y., L'Hours, H., Lindlar, M., Mehl, F., Mendes de Farias, T., Middlebos, W., Parkes, O., ... Märkälä, A. (2025). D3.1 - Report on Discipline Requirements and Needs (V1.0). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15789261
R7	EOSC EDEN T1.2, Lindlar, M., Caron, B., Benauer, M., Kylander, J., Dekeyser, K., Addis, M., Levlin, M., Laukkanen, M., Lehtonen, J., Burger, F., Koho, T., Schwab, F., Molloy, L., & Zhang, F. (2025). M1.1 Report on Identification of Core Preservation Processes. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16992452
R8	Hugo, W and Beck, J. Deliverable number: 5.2 - Guidance on Data Policy and Supporting Open Licences - Data Policy Considerations, Project: 730995 - Supporting EU-African Cooperation on Research Infrastructures for Food Security and Greenhouse Gas Observations (SEACRIFOG), 2019, http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11940.04485
R9	European Commission, 2018. Ethics and Data Protection, https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2020-06/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection_0.pdf
R10	W3C (2025), Community Group Report - Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV), https://w3c.github.io/dpv/primer/
R11	W3C (2018), ODRL Information Model 2.2, https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/
R12	Various (2025), Data Use Ontology, https://github.com/EBISPOT/DUO
R13	Carroll, S.R., Garba, I., Figueroa-Rodríguez, O.L., Holbrook, J., Lovett, R., Materechera, S., Parsons, M., Raseroka, K., Rodriguez-Lonebear, D., Rowe, R., Sara, R., Walker, J.D., Anderson, J. and Hudson, M. (2020) 'The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance', Data Science Journal, 19(1), p. 43. Available at: https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-043

R14	Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. <i>Scientific Data</i> , 3, 160018. https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18
R15	Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I., Downs, R. R., Edmunds, R., Giaretta, D., De Giusti, M., L'Hours, H., Hugo, W., Jenkyns, R., Khodiyar, V., Martone, M. E., Mokrane, M., Navale, V., Petters, J., Sierman, B., Sokolova, D. V., Stockhouse, M., & Westbrook, J. (2020). The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. <i>Scientific Data</i> , 7, 144. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7
R16	CoDATA (2025), Policy Brief: Data ethics and structural inequities in science, https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/13kbKucOclbflTMzygaAZc-l0XtkqblY6
R17	CoDATA (2025), POLICY BRIEF: Ethics and Indigenous Data Governance, https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/13kbKucOclbflTMzygaAZc-l0XtkqblY6
R18	CoDATA (2025), POLICY BRIEF: Privacy, https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/13kbKucOclbflTMzygaAZc-l0XtkqblY6
R19	CoDATA (2025), POLICY BRIEF: Data Ethics and Research integrity, https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/13kbKucOclbflTMzygaAZc-l0XtkqblY6
R20	GDPR.EU (2025), Writing a GDPR-compliant privacy notice, https://gdpr.eu/privacy-notice/
R21	European Union. (2016). Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). <i>Official Journal of the European Union</i> , L 119, 1–88. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj
R22	European Union. (2021). Regulation (EU) 2021/695 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013. <i>Official Journal of the European Union</i> , L 170, 1–68. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2021/695/oj
R23	Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity. (2011). Nagoya Protocol on access to genetic resources and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from their utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity: Text and annex. <i>United Nations Treaty Series</i> , 3109, 3. https://www.cbd.int/abs/
R24	General Services Administration. (2020). Federal Data Strategy – Data Ethics Framework. U.S. Federal Government. Retrieved from https://resources.data.gov/assets/documents/fds-data-ethics-framework.pdf
R25	CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements 2023-2025 Extended Guidance (V01.00). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051096
R26	EOSC EDEN T1.2, Lindlar, M., Caron, B., Benauer, M., Kylander, J., Dekeyser, K., Addis, M., Levlin, M., Laukkanen, M., Lehtonen, J., Burger, F., Koho, T., Schwab, F., Molloy, L., & Zhang, F. (2025). M1.1 Report on Identification of Core Preservation Processes. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16992452
R27	European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, EOSC Executive Board, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., Ojsteršek, M., Choirat, C., Sanden, M. v. d., & Coppens, F. (2021). EOSC interoperability framework : report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture, Publications Office. https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649

R28	RDA-CODATA Legal Interoperability Interest Group. (2016). Legal Interoperability of Research Data: Principles and Implementation Guidelines. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.162241
R29	EOSC Association AISBL. (2025). EOSC Federation Handbook (First Edition, March 27, 2025). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577
R30	CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements 2023-2025 Extended Guidance (V01.00). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051096
R31	PREMIS Editorial Committee, Rights Working Group. (2024). The 2022 revision of PREMIS rights white paper. Library of Congress. https://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/premis-rights-whitepaper-20240408.pdf
R32	Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS). (2024). Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS) (Magenta Book, CCSDS 650.0-M-3, Issue 3, December 2024). Washington, D.C.: CCSDS Secretariat. https://ccsds.org/wp-content/uploads/gravity_forms/5-448e85c647331d9cbaf66c096458bdd5/2025/01//650x0m3.pdf
R33	Hugo, W., & van Kemenade, J. (2023, September 21). Harmonising access procedures for sensitive data [Conference presentation]. EOSC Conference. Retrieved from https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/Harmonising-Access-Procedures-for-Sensitive-Data.pdf
R34	Cox, Krista L., "Metadata and Copyright: Should Institutions License Their Data about Scholarship?" (2017). Copyright, Fair Use, Scholarly Communication, etc.. 59. http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/scholcom/59
R35	van Horik, R., & Hugo, W. (2024). D3.3 - Guidelines for creating a user tailored EOSC Compliant PID Policy (V2.0 - DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14092489
R36	Thorogood, A. (2022). GDPR brief: Data protection implications of publishing metadata to enable discovery. Global Alliance for Genomics and Health. https://www.ga4gh.org/news_item/ga4gh-gdpr-brief-data-protection-implications-of-publishing-metadata-to-enable-discovery/
R37	European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. (2018). Ethics and data protection (14 November 2018). Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/ethics-guide-data-protection_en.pdf
R38	Hugo, W., Ulrich, R., L'Hours, H., Parkes, O., Davidson, J., & Ramezani, P. (2025). D5.3 - Final recommendations on implementing and exposing FAIR assessment for data and code (V1.0 - Not yet approved by the EC). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15534285
R39	European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, & EOSC Executive Board. (2021). EOSC Rules of Participation. Publications Office of the European Union. https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/a96d6233-554e-11eb-b59f-01aa75ed71a1
R40	RDA-CODATA Legal Interoperability Interest Group. (2016). Legal Interoperability of Research Data: Principles and Implementation Guidelines. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.162241
R41	Middelbos, W., Addis, M., Hugo, W., Steinhoff, W., Snyder, K. P., Wijngaarden, M., Presser, K., Cieřła, M., Le Meur, J.-Y., Koho, T., Kylander, J., Lehtonen, J., Levlin, M., Laukkanen, M., Dekeyser, K., Huber, R., Weiser, J., Høier, S., & Caron, B. (2025). EOSC EDEN T2.1 Detailed gathered

	requirements & specifications (1.0.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17142431
R42	Middelbos, W., Addis, M., Hugo, W., Steinhoff, W., Snyder, K. P., Wijngaarden, M., Presser, K., Cieśła, M., Le Meur, J.-Y., Koho, T., Kylander, J., Laukkanen, M., Lehtonen, J., Levlin, M., Dekeyser, K., Huber, R., Weiser, J., Høier, S., & Caron, B. (2025). EOSC EDEN T2.1 Gathered Considerations & Aspects and Attribute Identification, Services (1.0.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17119752
R44	L'Hours, H., Kleemola, M., Parkes, O., Recker, J., Duvaud, S., van Horik, R., Alaterä, T. J., Liberante, F., Conzett, P., Kaartinen, H., Bäckman, S., & Esteves, E. (2025). FIDELIS TTRAMatrix v00.02 Guide (v00.02). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15676189

Appendices

Appendix A: Repository Attributes

A.1 Sources of Attributes

Repository attributes are obtained from multiple sources, and these sources need to be recorded as references and provenance confirmation. Table A.1.1 provides selection of these sources, as well as URIs by which they can be referenced in data. The list does not contain all references, these are maintained in full in a supplementary listing.

Table A.1.1 Sources of Repository Attributes

#	URI	Title	Description
1	eden.WP1	Work Package 1	The attributes (or services) were identified as part of the work in EDEN WP1
2	eden.WP2	Work Package 2	The attributes (or services) were identified as part of the work in EDEN WP2
3	eden.WP3	Work Package 3	The attributes (or services) were identified as part of the work in EDEN WP3
4	fidelis.TTRAM	TTRAM	The attributes (or services) were identified as part of the work in FIDELIS WP5, resulting in the TTRAM
5	rda.TRSP	TRSP	The attributes were consolidated by the RDA Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group.

A.2 Attribute Properties

Repository attributes can have multiple properties, and these are defined and described in Table A.2.1

Table A.2.1 Repository Attribute Properties

#	URI prefix	Property	Description	Cardinality
1	eden:property.uri	URI	The unambiguous reference to the attribute	1
2	eden:property.name	Name	Name, label, or title of the attribute	1
3	eden:property.desc	Description	A description of the attribute	1
4	eden:property.privacy	Privacy	Whether the attribute is justifiably private. From A.2.3.1	1
5	eden:property.lod	Linked URIs	One or more other URIs for the attribute	0..n
6	eden:property.source	Source	The preferred source of information for the attribute. From A.2.3.2	1
7	eden:property.source.path	Path	The path, element or identifier of the property in the source	6→1
8	eden:property.source.agg	Aggregate	The style of aggregation of the attribute. From A.2.3.3	1

9	eden.property.source.criterion	Criterion	For some aggregation options, described in A.3.3.1, a criterion must also be provided	8→0..1
10	eden.property.source.profile	Profile	Any profile(s) associated with this repository attribute. Values from A.5.1	0..n

A.3 Controlled Vocabulary for Attribute Description

A.3.1 Privacy

Table A.3.1.1 Repository Attribute Privacy

URI prefix	Property	Description	Cardinality
eden:privacy.public	Public	Property MUST be public.	1
eden:privacy.private	Private	Property MAY be private	1

A.3.2 Attribute Sources

Table A.3.2.1 Repository Attribute Source

URI prefix	Property	Description	Cardinality
eden:source.fairicat	FAIRiCAT	The property is obtained via a FAIRiCAT implementation	0..1
eden:source.fairicat.type	FAIRiCAT Implementation Target	If the FAIRiCAT option is selected, information can be at one of the following locations: WKU: Well-Known URL HOME: Home Page	0..1
eden:source.fairicat.std	FAIRiCAT Encoding	If the FAIRiCAT option is selected, information can be encoded as follows: HEAD: Information is provided as links in the HTTP HEAD HEAD-LINK: The HEAD points to a JSON Linkset File HTML-SCHEMA: The information is obtained from schema.org embedded in the HTML Header. HTML-DCAT: The information is obtained from DCAT embedded in the HTML Header.	0..1
eden:source.registry	Registry	The property is obtained via a registry entry	0..1

A.3.3 Aggregation

Table A.3.3.1 Repository Attribute Aggregation Options

URI prefix	Property	Description
eden:aggregation.none	None	Use the value retrieved as presented, no processing required
eden:aggregation.list	List	An array of values is returned, convert the array to a comma-delimited list of unique occurrences
eden:aggregation.sum	Sum	An array of values is returned, convert the array to a sum of the values

eden:aggregation.ave	Average	An array of values is returned, convert the array to an average of the values
eden:aggregation.max	Maximum	An array of values is returned, convert the array to a maximum of the values
eden:aggregation.min	Minimum	An array of values is returned, convert the array to a minimum of the values
eden:aggregation.frac	Fraction	Convert the result to a fraction of array elements meeting a criterion. The criterion is specified as an additional attribute property.
eden:aggregation.facets	Facets	Provide a count by facet from a two-dimensional array response, with the facet values based on the criterion specified as an additional attribute property.
eden:aggregation.weighted	Weighted	Provide a weighted average from a two-dimensional array response, with the weight values based on the criterion specified as an additional attribute property.
eden.aggregation.API	API	Submit the value of the attribute to an API and record the response

A.4 Repository Attributes

This is a working list of repository attributes, gathered from a variety of sources (these are described in A.1). The list does not contain additional repository attribute properties as described in A.2. The full dataset of attributes is maintained elsewhere¹¹⁷.

Table A.4.1 Repository Attributes Master List

#	URI	Attribute	Description	Reference
1	eden:attribute.alignment.policy	Alignment Policy	The repository provides an alignment policy or submission guidelines that assists depositors with determining whether the repository is appropriate for their deposit	4.1.1.1-01
2	eden:attribute.alignment.verify	Alignment Verification	The repository verifies, manually or automatically, that a submission aligns with the repository objectives and mandate expressed in the guidance or policy	4.1.1.1-01
3	eden:attribute.alignment.service	Alignment Service	The repository offers a service to determine if the context and content of a submission aligns with their guidance and policies	4.1.1.1-01
4	eden:attribute.alignment.service.api	Alignment Service API Endpoint	The URL to the service endpoint API to assist depositors with repository selection.	4.1.1.1-01
5	eden:attribute.alignment.service.ui	Alignment Service UI	The URL to the service UI to assist depositors with repository selection.	4.1.1.1-01
6	eden:attribute.dependencies.verify	Dependencies Verification	The repository verifies that datasets are self-contained, in other words do not	4.1.1.1-02

¹¹⁷ Full repository attribute dataset

			require additional dependencies to be reused.	
7	eden.attribute.documentation.verify	Documentation Verification	The repository verifies that datasets have adequate documentation for purposes of reuse.	4.1.1.1-03
8	eden.attribute.rights.consent.verify	Rights Holder Consent Verification	The repository verifies that rights holders have consented to publication in the repository.	4.1.1.1-04
9	eden.attribute.authors.consent.verify	Author Consent Verification	The repository verifies all listed authors have consented to publication in the repository.	4.1.1.1-04
10	eden.attribute.context.verify	Submission Context Verification	The repository verifies that the submissions received emanate from credible research sources, by verifying identity, affiliation, and other context indicators such as a link to a DMP, RO-Crate, or a peer-reviewed publication.	4.1.1.1-05 4.1.1.1-06
11	eden.attribute.integrity.fraud.verify	Submission - Fraud Detection	The repository takes steps to determine whether submissions contain any fraudulent content.	4.1.1.1-07
12	eden.attribute.integrity.content.verify	Submission - Inappropriate Content	The repository has measures in place to detect inappropriate, malicious, or illegal content.	4.1.1.1-08 4.1.1.1-09
13	eden.attribute.sensitive.policy	Sensitive Data Policy	The repository has a sensitive data policy that addresses detection, classification, and management of sensitive data	4.1.1.1-10
14	eden.attribute.sensitive.verify	Sensitive Data Verification	The repository verifies submissions in terms of the policy	4.1.1.1-10
15	eden.attribute.sensitive.licence.guidance	Sensitive Data Licence	The repository offers guidance in respect of sensitive data licence selection	4.1.1.1-10
16	eden.attribute.sensitive.licence.list	Data Licence List	The list of URI references to the licences offered by the repository.	4.1.1.1-10

A.5 Repository Profiles

The primary list of repository attributes is an aggregation of the needs, requirements, and existing implementations from a wide-ranging list of sources.

Table A.5.1 Repository Attribute Profile Sources

#	URI	Profile	Description
1	eden:profile.cts	CoreTrustSeal	The repository attributes implied by CoreTrustSeal certification criteria and guidelines
2	eden:profile.ccp	Core Preservation Processes	Repository attributes associated with core preservation processes identified in EDEN WP1

3	eden.profile.ttram	TTRAM	Repository attributes associated with repository actions and attributes identified in FIDELIS WP5
4	eden.profile.trsp.sp	TRSP - Service Providers	Repository attributes associated with repository service providers identified in the RDA WG on Community Criteria for TRSPs
5	eden.profile.trsp.soft	TRSP - Software Platforms	Repository attributes associated with software platforms identified in the RDA WG on Community Criteria for TRSPs
6	eden.profile.trsp.code	TRSP - Code Repositories	Repository attributes associated with code repositories identified in the RDA WG on Community Criteria for TRSPs

Appendix B: Services

B.1 Service Inventory

A list of all identified services can be found in a separately published annex¹¹⁸ in the sheet ‘Services’.

B.2 Supporting Vocabulary

B.2.1 Technology Readiness Levels

The following technology readiness levels apply to services, as promoted by the European Commission:

Table B.2.1.1: Technology Readiness Levels

#	URI	Description	Reference
1	eden:trl.1	Basic principles observed	[R2], [R3]
2	eden:trl.2	Technology concept formulated	[R2], [R3]
3	eden:trl.3	Experimental proof of concept	[R2], [R3]
4	eden:trl.4	Technology validated in lab	[R2], [R3]
5	eden:trl.5	Technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)	[R2], [R3]
6	eden:trl.6	Technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)	[R2], [R3]
7	eden:trl.7	System prototype demonstration in operational environment	[R2], [R3]
8	eden:trl.8	System complete and qualified	[R2], [R3]
9	eden:trl.9	Actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)	[R2], [R3]

B.2.2 Service Properties

The following properties are required to adequately describe a service. The list of properties are an extension of the CodeMeta schema for software [R4]. While we would expect all services developed by EOSC EDEN to maintain a minimum CodeMeta record, we also list those properties that were identified from other sources and coincide with CodeMeta properties. In many cases, the CodeMeta URI derives from other sources (schema.org, for example) - we then also list these.

Table B.2.2.1: Service Properties

#	URI prefix	Property	Description	Cardinality	Reference
1	eden:property.uri codemeta:identifier schema:identifier	URI	The unambiguous identifier for the service	1	[R4]
2	eden:property.name codemeta:name schema:name	Title	The name, title, or label associated with the service	1	[R4]

¹¹⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17119752>

3	eden:property.desc codemeta:description schema:description	Description	A description of the service	1	[R4]
4	eden:property.url	URL	One or more URLs to resources associated with the service	1..n	[R4]
5	eden:property.url.type	URL Type	One of several types of URL	4→1..n	[R4]

B.2.3 Service URL Types

The following table provides a type vocabulary for URLs associated with a service. The list is based on several sources: It takes into account the information that may be required to construct a JSON-LD Affordances definition based on the FAIRiCAT specification [R5].

Table B.2.3.1 URL Types

#	URI	Description
1	eden:url.type.url	Any URL that can be used to access the service by end users
2	eden:url.type.api	An API for the service
3	eden:url.type.ui	A user interface for the service
4	eden:url.type.git	A git-based code repository for the service
5	eden:url.type.doc	Technical documentation for the service
6	eden:url.type.guide	End user guidance for the service

Appendix C: Design Considerations

C.1 Aspects

This section provides a partial inventory of aspects for the purposes of illustration, together with the repository attributes associated with them. A comprehensive listing is provided elsewhere¹¹⁹.

Table C.1.1: Examples of Aspects Identified per Design Consideration

Consideration	Aspect	Description	Identified attributes
Format Fragmentation in Research Data	Support for both General-purpose and Domain-specific Formats	Does the repository publish information about which type of data and which formats it supports for preservation?	Publishes which types of information the repository stores in a machine-readable interface. (software, analysis, raw data) Publish policies and refers them with persistent URI about formatting of file formats to a desired type by the repository
Format Fragmentation in Research Data	Metadata Alignment across Heterogeneous Formats	Does the repository support the ability to map, transform and/or align metadata that comes in different schemas, standards, or structural formats?	Publishes a list of supported metadata schemas Publishes a list which metadata schemas can be crosswalked
Format Fragmentation in Research Data	Integration Tools for Bridging Formats	Does the repository use services or tools which are also available to translate, transform, mediate between different data formats (e.g. package structures, file formats, metadata standards)?	Publishes URI to service or documentation for a transformation service if such service is available Publishes the tools used for this service Publishes if the service or tool is part of a workflow, such as ingestion, validations ...)
Format Fragmentation in Research Data	Support for Different Packaging Standards	Does the repository have the capability to accept, produce or convert between different packaging standards?	Publishes a list of packaging standards which are accepted? Publishes a list of packaging standards the service or tools can produce Publishes the packaging standard used by the repository internally Publishes a list of packaging standards in can converts to Publishes a list of community-specific packaging standards it supports Publishes if the services or tools auto-discover the used packaging standard on ingest.
Lack of Federated Discovery Across Domain	Top-level and fine-grained search mechanisms	Does the repository support high-level and/or detailed level search?	Repository or Archive support high level searching Repository or Archive support low level searching Publish list of searchable metadata fields Support for filtering based on content properties Response format of search service Supported harvesting protocols Does the repository accept data from other sources than its own serving community? Publishes which metadata standards the repository supports Publishes which protocol is used for harvesting Publishes if the repository supports crosswalks

¹¹⁹[R42] in the sheet 'Aspects'

			Publishes documentation about versioning
Lack of Federated Discovery Across Domain	Federated and cross-domain query support	Is the system capable of querying across domains to participate in external cross-domain discovery networks?	Can query multiple external sources from one interface Supported protocols for federated search List to machine-readable registry of known external queryable sources Is the search real time or done after harvesting or indexing Can the end user filter by disciplinary domain or repository List or indexed or harvested sources
Lack of Federated Discovery Across Domain	Metadata indexing at multiple levels	Is the system able to index metadata at different levels (e.g. dataset level, file level, service level)?	List of indexed metadata levels per source URI to access indexed metadata Frequency of updating the index Format of the indexed data Which levels are exposed to harvesters Index profile or standard used
Lack of Federated Discovery Across Domain	Discovery APIs supporting varying granularity	Does the system have APIs or interfaces for data and metadata that support queries at multiple levels of granularity focusing on the internal capability for a repository being able to expose rich, multilevel discovery?	URL to discovery api Granularity levels which are supported List of fields that can be queried per each level of granularity Query language used Support for linked entity resolution Result format of the API Support for pagination Metadata standards used by the API
Persistent Identifier (PID) Diversity and Policy Gaps	Cross-community PID harmonisation	Does the repository make use of Persistent Identifiers (PID)?	Publishes which persistent identifier standards it supports in a machine-readable way Repository publishes its policy for PID? Does the repository resolve external PIDs? Can a PID be linked to objects in another domain? Is PID metadata exposed in a machine-readable format?
Persistent Identifier (PID) Diversity and Policy Gaps	Machine-resolvable PIDs	Does the repository have the capability to autoresolve metadata based on PIDs?	Is the PID globally unique? Is the PID resolvable via HTTPS? Does the PID resolve to a machine-readable landing page with metadata? Does the resolver of the PID support different formats of metadata Supported metadata formats for the PID by the API Latency inf resolution of the PID Which type of PID is used in the repository
Persistent Identifier (PID) Diversity and Policy Gaps	Metadata-linked identifiers	Does the repository support PID which are connected to structured descriptive metadata?	Does the PID link to structured metadata? The format of the exposed metadata Is the structured metadata resolvable only using the PID? The metadata conforms to which standard? Metadata includes provenance data? Endpoint to retrieve metadata linked to PID
Persistent Identifier (PID) Diversity and Policy Gaps	Clear EOSC PID policy and lifecycle tracking	Does the repository have clear policies, procedures and systems to manage the lifecycle of Persistent Identifiers?	Link to policy of assignment & reassignment and deprecation of PIDs Does the PID system tracks different versions of a object Does the PID metadata include lifecycle status?

			Are changes to metadata or PID records logged and timestamped? Which global PID initiatives are aligned with the repository policy?
Standards-Based Authentication Mechanisms	Standards Support	Does the repository or service implement widely accepted authentication and authorisation protocols such as SAML, OpenID Connect, or OAuth2? Supporting well-established standards ensures compatibility with federated identity providers, secure machine-to-machine communication, and interoperability with EOSC's AAI ecosystem. This also facilitates cross-service user access and integration with external infrastructures.	Which authentication standards are supported? Does the service support login via institutional or federated identity providers? Are authentication mechanisms compliant with EOSC AAI recommendations? Is there technical documentation outlining supported protocols and endpoints?
Lack of Metadata Harmonisation Across Domains	Support for domain-specific metadata profiles	Does the TDR or TDA have the capability to expose metadata that is following community- or discipline-specific metadata profiles in addition to generic standards.	What is the default metadata profile which is used? Does the system let users select a metadata profile? Is the metadata validated against its profile? Does the system give references to the documentation of each profile? The system is giving a url, on which the schema can be found machine-readable Are there any crosswalks available and from and to the metadata schemas? Does the system register its profile to a community registry? Support extension of profiles?
Lack of Metadata Harmonisation Across Domains	Crosswalks between metadata schemas	Does the TDR or TDA ensure that after the crosswalks the meaning of the metadata across systems by the presence of semantic mapping?	List of schema pairs with defined mappings Indication if the mappings are machine-readable URI to human-readable documentation about the crosswalk If the semantic mappings are tested for semantic correctness?
Lack of Metadata Harmonisation Across Domains	Multilingual metadata support	Is the system able to provide the metadata in different languages to give people from different backgrounds the ability to interpret them consistently?	List of supported languages Do metadata fields include language tags? Does the system support multilingual search? If the metadata fields are available in more than one language?
Lack of Metadata Harmonisation Across Domains	Schema.org or FAIR-compliant metadata exposure	Whether the system is exposing the metadata in a structured, machine-readable format aligned with FAIR principles?	FAIR formats used and supported by the system? If the system supports multiple formats If the system adherence to a specific type of metadata model or profile
Lack of Metadata Harmonisation Across Domains	Reference repositories for semantic artefacts	Does the TDR or TDA ensure that semantic artefacts used in metadata are discoverable and accessible through domain-recognised reference repositories to promote reuse, semantic consistency, and machine-actionability?	List of referenced semantic repositories Presence of PIDs for artefacts Human-readable documentation URI

Inconsistent Use of Controlled Vocabularies and Ontologies	Use of community-endorsed controlled vocabularies	Whether the system is making use of standard and authoritative vocabularies for metadata elements to enhance shared understanding.	System publishes a list of controlled vocabularies it uses Which vocabularies are relevant for the domain of the system List of metadata fields which use controlled vocabularies and which
Inconsistent Use of Controlled Vocabularies and Ontologies	Machine-readable vocabulary linking	Whether the system has the capability to expose the controlled vocabularies and ontologies terms in such format it is machine-readable which increases metadata interpretation, reasoning and integration across systems automatically.	Publishes a list of machine-readable formats it is supporting Publishes URIs which resolve to a useful representation of terms Which well known namespaces are used in the metadata URI or reference to documentation for the vocabulary of use API which offers an endpoint to query or explore linked vocabularies
Inconsistent Use of Controlled Vocabularies and Ontologies	Vocabulary harmonisation and mapping services	Whether the system has services available to align or map terms across different vocabularies or ontologies. These mappings ensure semantical equivalent terms for a wide variety of communities which this way can be interpreted consistently.	List of available mappings between vocabularies Supported mapping services Standard mapping formats
Lack of Persistent, Resolvable Identifiers for Semantic Entities	Use of PIDs for semantic terms	Whether the system is supporting PID for semantic terms	Which metadata values are associated with URI-based identifiers Which authoritative sources are used for entities Which identifiers are supported
Lack of Persistent, Resolvable Identifiers for Semantic Entities	Support for semantic identifier dereferencing	Whether the system is supported and that the URI referencing structured information is resolvable.	Whether the identifiers used in metadata can be dereferenced Whether the identifiers return structured machine-readable data
Lack of Persistent, Resolvable Identifiers for Semantic Entities	Alignment with recognised identifier systems	Whether the system is aligned with well-established identifier systems for common metadata entities, which increases the discoverability and reuse.	Indicates which established PID systems are supported and used URI to the system policy for PIDs types and formats
Lack of Persistent, Resolvable Identifiers for Semantic Entities	Support for multilingual vocabularies	Whether the system is aligned with well-established identifier systems for common metadata entities, which increases the discoverability and reuse.	Indicates which established PID systems are supported and used URI to the system policy for PIDs types and formats
Fragmentation of Semantic Annotation Practices	Support for embedded semantic annotations	Whether the system supports embedded semantic annotations.	Whether metadata can include embedded semantic structures Publishes context or vocabularies used in the semantic markup
Fragmentation of Semantic Annotation Practices	External annotation services or tools	Whether the system supports and uses external tools or services for applying, managing and/or enriching metadata with semantic annotations. Possibly enabling decoupled annotation workflows.	Whether the system supports the integration of external platforms for annotate metadata Whether semantic annotations can be bound to objects via PIDs Whether the system provides interfaces for manual or assisted semantic enrichment
Fragmentation of Semantic Annotation Practices	SLA semantics	Does the service clearly and consistently define the semantics of its Service-Level Agreements (SLAs) in a way that is interpretable both by humans	Does the system publish the SLAs in a machine-readable format? Which vocabulary does the system use for the SLAs?

		and machines across communities?	Does the system link to a human-readable version of the SLA? Is the system declaring community-aligned definitions for services attributes such as uptime, ticket response time ..?
Misalignment of Institutional Policies	Repository has a publicly accessible data policy webpage	Whether the repository publishes its data policy in a clearly accessible location on its website, so external partners can understand the conditions and frameworks governing data access, reuse, and preservation.	If the repository data policy is publicly available online Where the data policy is located If the policy is linked from metadata or landing pages
Misalignment of Institutional Policies	Policy includes machine-readable terms	Whether the repository's data policy is encoded in a structured, machine-readable format (e.g., JSON-LD, XML, RDF), allowing automated tools and external systems to ingest, assess, or integrate policy information.	If the policy includes embedded machine-readable metadata Which format or encoding is used If specific access and reuse conditions are semantically tagged If tools can automatically parse license or policy clauses
Misalignment of Institutional Policies	Policy includes versioning information	Whether the repository maintains and displays version history of its data policy, enabling traceability and clarity over policy changes for users and collaborators.	If the policy document includes a version number or date If a changelog or revision history is maintained If older versions of the policy are archived and accessible If changes between versions are documented
Inconsistent Service Workflows	Standardised Data Deposit Process	Whether the system supports a harmonised, community-aligned workflow for data publication and deposit. This includes ensuring that data providers follow agreed protocols for metadata generation, format selection, validation, and submission. The standardisation of deposit workflows fosters interoperability, simplifies reuse, and ensures consistent metadata quality across domains.	Whether the system enforces the use of community-agreed metadata standards during deposit Whether there is a defined sequence of steps for data publication Whether data deposits are linked to persistent identifiers and versioned consistently Whether machine-actionable APIs are available to support automated or assisted deposit processes
Undefined Roles and Responsibilities	Published Service Ownership	Whether the system provides publicly available information on the ownership, custodianship, or stewardship of services and components. This includes identifying the responsible individuals or entities for service operation, maintenance, and decision-making, which enhances transparency and accountability within EOSC.	Whether service ownership is clearly documented and published. Whether the owning organization or contact point is persistently identified. Whether changes in service ownership are tracked and versioned over time. Whether ownership metadata is exposed through service catalogues or registries.
Undefined Roles and Responsibilities	Role Metadata in Deposit and Curation	Whether systems capture and expose metadata about individual and organizational roles involved in the deposit, curation, maintenance, and management of digital objects. This includes identifying roles such as data steward, curator,	Whether role-based metadata is included in the object or collection's metadata. Whether roles are linked to persistent identifiers Whether systems allow role assignment during data submission and curation processes.

		depositor, reviewer, or administrator.	Whether provenance of role-related actions is recorded and auditable.
Lack of User-Centric Service Design	Accessibility and Support Documentation	Whether the system provides clear, user-friendly pathways for users to access, understand, and effectively use its services, particularly in cross-disciplinary or multi-platform research environments. This includes the availability of comprehensive documentation, tutorials, help interfaces, and support services that lower the barrier to entry and promote effective onboarding. Accessibility also refers to the clarity of service offerings, consistency in interfaces, and ease of locating and using relevant resources.	Whether the system provides structured, up-to-date user documentation and tutorials. Whether multilingual or discipline-specific help resources are available. Whether user support services are integrated and accessible.
Federated Identity and Trust Frameworks	Federated Identity Support	Does the repository or service allow users to authenticate using their existing institutional or research infrastructure credentials? Federated identity support ensures users don't need to create new accounts for every service, enabling secure, scalable access.	Does the repository support login through federated identity providers? Which identity providers or infrastructures are supported? Are group/role memberships provided by identity providers accepted and mapped? Are metadata attributes from the identity provider utilised?
License Compatibility and Reusability	License alignment and combinability	Ensures that licenses applied to datasets and metadata can be legally combined or reused across different systems or domains. This is crucial in collaborative research where data from multiple sources is aggregated or remixed.	Indicates which licenses are used by the repository Publishes compatibility matrix or guidance on combining licenses Provides guidance for users on how to choose combinable licenses
License Compatibility and Reusability	Use of standardised open licenses	Repositories and services should adopt well-known, standardised open licenses to reduce legal uncertainty and support broad reuse across domains.	Lists supported license types URI to license policy Indicates default license applied if none is provided by depositor
Clarity and Automation of Legal Conditions	Machine-readable licensing terms	Licensing information should be machine-readable to allow systems to automatically process and enforce legal conditions for access and reuse.	Metadata includes license in machine-readable format Declares which standard vocabularies or schemas are used for licenses URI to machine-readable license expression
Clarity and Automation of Legal Conditions	Metadata describing access and use conditions	Access rights and usage conditions for data should be clearly expressed in metadata to inform users and enable automated decision-making.	Metadata includes access condition fields Standard terms or controlled vocabularies used URI pointing to detailed access policy
Restriction Handling and Compliance	Embargos, redaction, and generalisation mechanisms	Systems should implement mechanisms to restrict data where required (e.g., embargo periods, redaction of sensitive parts, data generalisation) in line with legal or ethical requirements.	Supports embargo expiration and enforcement Supports data redaction or obfuscation workflows Metadata indicates if data has been generalised or redacted

Restriction Handling and Compliance	Documentation of applicable restrictions	Systems should publish documentation explaining the legal or ethical restrictions applied to datasets, ensuring transparency for end users and systems.	URI to restriction policy or legal guidance Metadata includes justification for restriction Indicates responsible authority for applying the restriction
Policy and Regulatory Alignment	Alignment with EU and national data policies	Repositories and services should align with applicable legal frameworks, including GDPR and national open data laws, to ensure lawful access, storage, and sharing.	Declares alignment with GDPR and/or national policies URI to policy compliance statement Designates Data Protection Officer or authority
Policy and Regulatory Alignment	Evaluation of license mandates at different levels	License Compatibility and Reusability	Metadata includes license mandate information Lists relevant institutional/funding policies URI to documentation of license mandate checks
FAIR Metadata Despite Restrictions	Use of persistent identifiers for restricted data	Even if a dataset cannot be openly shared, it should still be assigned a persistent identifier (PID) so it can be discovered, cited, and tracked across systems.	PID is assigned to restricted datasets PID resolves to restricted-access landing page Metadata includes explanation of access conditions
FAIR Metadata Despite Restrictions	Publishing of access policies even for restricted content	Repositories should expose access policies for restricted datasets in a machine-readable way so that users and automated systems can understand access limitations.	Access policies are publicly available Machine-readable access policy formats supported URI to access condition documentation
Transparency of Access and Rights	Publication Consent	Have all the rights owners to the work consented to its submission to the repository and its publication?	Rightsholder consent obtained
Authenticity and Originality	Research Origin Verified	The repository verifies that the submission was made by a researcher or someone making a deposit in a research context, and that it is a dataset associated with original research	Depositor context verified maDMP is available and linked Peer-reviewed publication linked
Authenticity and Originality	Provenance	Repositories can inspect provenance metadata to confirm the authenticity of work submitted for publication	Provenance verified RO-Crate record exists and is linked
Ethics Considerations	Fraud	The repository takes precautions to detect and reject fraudulent submissions	Statistical integrity verification Plagiarism check performed Duplicate publication verified
Ethics Considerations	Inappropriate Content	The repository takes measures to identify and reflect inappropriate content	Checked for malicious content Checked for nonsense or irrelevant content
Legal and Contractual Aspects	Illegal Content	The repository verifies that illegal content is not included in the deposit.	Legality of content verified
Legal and Contractual Aspects	GDPR	The repository verifies whether personal data is included in the deposit, and if so, follows a procedure to determine the level	Personal/ Sensitive Data Policy exists Object or submission is tested for sensitivity Object is verified against policy Sensitive data licences available

		of protection required and implements it	
Unclear permissions	Right statement standardisation	The repository transparently exposes standardised right statements	Metadata standards supporting explicit indication of access rights Generic vocabulary used to describe rights (ODRL)
Unclear permissions	Access rights	The repository clearly indicates access rights	Access rights statement given Standard vocabulary for access rights used
Unclear permissions	Usage rights	The repository clearly indicates usage rights	Usage rights / Terms of Use given Standard vocabulary for usage rights used
Unclear permissions	Publishing rights	The repository clearly indicates publication rights	Publication rights given Standard vocabulary for publication rights used
Licensing conflicts	License standardisation	The repository uses commonly accepted machine-readable standard terms (or URIs) to indicate licenses	Metadata standards supporting explicit indication of licenses Standard vocabulary used for licenses Machine-readable licenses
Licensing conflicts	License guidance	The repository provides user guidance to select the most appropriate license	License selection tool available
Licensing conflicts	Licence provision	The repository maintains a registry or list of accepted licenses	Licence registry or dictionary available
Licensing conflicts	Licence stewardship	The repository regularly checks assigned licenses and has workflows in place to replace outdated or invalid licenses in a legally compliant manner.	Licenses are up to date
Inconsistent policies	Policy standardisation	The repository exposes policies in a standardised way.	Metadata standards supporting explicit indication of policies
Inconsistent policies	Policy (type) provision	The repository uses a controlled vocabulary to indicate the policy type of its policy documents.	Policy vocabulary used Policy documents indicate policy type in metadata
Legal uncertainty	Legal clearance	The repository provides mechanisms and tools to assess the legal compliance of its assets.	Legal compliance indicated in metadata Legal (self) assessment tool available
Ethical constraints	Ethics governance	The repository has mechanisms in place to report on ethical misconduct and has a contingency plan in place	Feedback mechanism implemented
Ethical constraints	Ethics clearance	The repository has tools to perform ethical assessments	Ethical compliance indicated in metadata Ethical (self) assessment tool available
Documentation gaps	Contract and consent management	The repository manages its users' contracts and consents and assigns them to individual digital objects as necessary such as preservation agreements etc.	Links to user related contracts and agreements available Contract and consent management system in place
Lack of well defined semantics for AIPs	Well defined semantics for each component of an AIP	There needs to be a mechanism that allows a TDA to describe each component of its AIPs in terms of the semantics that apply, for example which schemas, vocabularies and ontologies are being used. This includes the semantics of the	The TDA can demonstrate what semantic standards and specifications it follows for its holdings. The TDA can describe its holdings according to the semantics of the OAIS Information model.

		data in the AIP, the semantics of associated information such as provenance, fixity, rights and quality, and the contents of the AIP as defined by the semantics of the OAIS Information Model.	
Lack of well defined semantics for AIPs	Evaluation of AIPs against the semantics of the OAIS Information Model	A TDA shall be able to describe each component of its AIPs in terms of the OAIS Information Model so that the AIP can be evaluated for completeness and conformance to the OAIS information model. For example, which component of the AIP corresponds to PDI, Representation Information, Data Objects etc.	The TDA can map each component of its AIPs to a corresponding entity in the OAIS Information Model
Diverse range of formats and specifications used for AIPs	The technical details of each component of an AIP are well defined and at all levels.	There needs to be a mechanism that allows a TDA to describe each component of its AIPs in terms of the technical formats, specifications and standards that are used. For example, the formats used for metadata (e.g. json, CSV, XML etc), references to the schemas that apply (e.g. DataCite, DCAT etc.), the specifications used for layout (e.g. OCFL), the information package standards followed (e.g. E-ARK), the technical mapping to the OAIS Information Model, and how content is packaged for transfer (e.g. BagIt).	The TDA can describe the technical standards and specifications it follows for all aspects of serialising and packaging an AIP.
Lack of consistent approach to implementing the OAIS Information Model for AIPs	Evaluation of AIP contents against the components of the OAIS Information Model	A TDA should be able to check the extent to which an AIP conforms to the OAIS Information Model from a technical perspective. This includes whether the mapping to OAIS is syntactically correct, whether the claimed components of the OAIS Information Model are physically present in the AIP, and for each component whether they are technically conformant to their specified formats and schemas.	The TDA can show to what extent its AIPs conform to the requirements of OAIS.
Lack of well defined mechanism for exchanging AIPs between organisations and systems	Exchange of AIPs between organisations	There should be a well defined protocol and set of API endpoints that can be used to request and execute transfer of AIPs in whole or in part between organisations. This includes support for AIP versioning and synchronisation of AIP versions between organisations.	The TDA supports access to and exchange of its AIPs using a defined protocol and set of APIs.
Machine-readable rights for digital preservation of AIPs	Machine-readable rights specifications	Rights change over time and for a large number of AIPs the checks to ensure appropriate	The TDA can automatically check and confirm it has the legal basis for holding and preserving its AIPs.

		rights are in place can be burdensome. Therefore, rights statements need to be machine readable to support automated checks.	
Automated FAIR Metadata assessment	FAIR assessment tool	The repository should be transparent on which automated FAIR assessment tools it uses.	Which FAIR assessment tool(s) was used?
Automated FAIR Metadata assessment	FAIR assessment aggregated score	The curator, or the system includes a FAIR score in the deposit and publishes them on different levels.	FAIR assessment score available on object level FAIR assessment score on collection level FAIR assessment score on repository level
Automated FAIR Metadata assessment	Guidance on FAIR compliance	The repository/system publishes guidance on improvement of the FAIRness score of a deposit, so that a depositor can use this to improve the FAIRness of the deposit.	Expose guidance on FAIRness (API)
Metadata Completeness	Essential metadata fields	Data(set) submission includes all essential descriptive metadata elements required by the repository, so that the dataset can be understood and discovered in the future.	A repository defines mandatory metadata fields for deposits. Repository Curators verify metadata completeness. Repository uses deposit form validators.
Multilingual Metadata	Language Localization and indexation	A repository supports metadata in multiple languages to broaden accessibility. Providing translations for titles/abstracts or using multilingual thesauri for subjects.	A repository UI and schema allow for key metadata to be entered in more than one language. Multilingual vocabulary support is implemented.
Lack documented properties of files in a repository	Technical metadata extraction	The repository or service is able to extract relevant technical metadata from files based on the defined significant properties. Tools for metadata extraction exist for all file formats that are supported by the TDA.	Technical metadata is produced in a standardised, interoperable format. If technical metadata is extracted by using different tools, the outputs are harmonised and mapped to technical metadata standards.
Lack documented properties of files in a repository	Significant properties definition	The repository or service can define and document the significant properties of the supported file formats.	Machine-actionable templates for each file format supported by the TDA. Possible scoring or weighting of different significant properties. Documentation is used in workflows for planning and evaluating possible file format conversion paths and processes.
A repository does not know if files it preserves are well-formed and valid	File format validation	The repository or service is able to verify the well-formedness and validity of files. Validation should be performed on all file formats that are supported by the TDA.	Wrongly identified files are detected. The service ensures that the files can be accessed with contemporary software. Invalid files are identified with a detailed error message that describes the issue.
Files are corrupted, broken and unusable	File repair	The repository has a process for repairing invalid files.	Invalid files can be detected. Invalid files can be repaired according to a documented, standardised process.
Files are not in a supported or sustainable file format	Format normalisation	Files in unsupported formats are normalised to formats that are sustainable and suitable for digital preservation.	Files are in sustainable formats. The service provides guidance for high-quality format conversions.

Files are stored in file formats that are obsolete	Format migration	Files in formats that have become obsolete are migrated to formats that are sustainable.	Files are in sustainable formats. The service provides guidance for high-quality format conversions.
A repository does not have information on how to repair an invalid file	File format validation error database	The TDA should document commonly encountered file format validation errors and their solutions in a regularly maintained database.	Repository maintains a database that documents file format validation errors. Repository has defined a process for updating the database.
Files are not in a supported or sustainable file format	Format transformation tools registry	A registry that lists common tools for transforming file formats from format A to format B.	Repository is aware of tools that can be implemented for file format transformation actions.
Legal and Regulatory	Legal - GDPR Compliance	The repository verifies whether personal data is included in the deposit (including pseudonymised data), and if so, follows a procedure to determine the level of protection required and implements it	Personal/ Sensitive Data Policy exists Privacy Statement available Personal Data Removal Request Procedure exists Confirmation of personal data removal can be provided GDPR-Compliant Privacy Statement is available
Ethics Considerations	Ethics Clearance	The repository verifies to the best of its knowledge that outputs are the result of a research process for which ethics clearance was obtained, including provision for, and specifics of, data sharing when gaining consent.	Ethics clearance-related policy Consent forms are linked or available Ethics clearance documents are linked or available
Transparency of Access and Rights	Transparency	Repositories ensure that all access conditions, restrictions, or limitations are transparent, and preferably machine readable.	Machine-actionable licences used Provisions are encoded using a published vocabulary
Balancing Rights and Openness	TRUST-Access Conditions	Repositories ensure that access conditions are implemented and enforced.	Record of access requests and outcomes
Transparency of Access and Rights	Clarity	Repositories clearly indicate which licences are supported	List of supported licences
Transparency of Access and Rights	Granularity	Repositories should indicate the scope and applicability of the licence	Actors expected to act on the licence Scope of the licence: object level, dataset level, etc.
Licences and Machine Actionability	Re-appraisal	Repositories should re-appraise the objects in the repository from time to time, either with scheduled frequency or due to defined triggers.	Last date of re-appraisal, including licence re-appraisal
Balancing Rights and Openness	Disclosure Risk	Licences are one of the responses to an assessed disclosure risk, the others include anonymisation/ pseudonymisation, adding synthetic data, and type of storage and access management.	Evidence of a disclosure risk assessment process
Open Metadata and Bibliographic Information	Metadata	Repositories should explicitly state that bibliographic data and non-sensitive metadata are available under a CC0 licence.	Licence in use for metadata (bibliographic, non-sensitive) Include metadata/ bibliographic data in privacy statement

Policy and Regulatory Alignment	Subject Protection	Repositories should indicate the relevant policy that addresses its provisions for protection of subject rights, confirmation or verification of ethics concerns, and compliance with legal obligations	Evidence of policy addressing ethics and rights Evidence of an ethics and rights-focused checklist for curators and depositors
Ethical constraints	Attribution	Repositories clearly state the need for proper attribution of content that is reused	Evidence of guidelines for reuse or conditions of use Licence assent is recorded
Policy and Regulatory Alignment	Inventory	Repositories should make a list of applicable policies available in a machine-readable way	Policy inventory list with links to latest copies
Sovereignty	Infrastructure Location	Repositories may want to indicate to end users where their resources are stored physically Data security and integrity information	Data security and integrity information Indication of locality (country) of data storage
Lack of Metadata Harmonisation Across Domains	The efficient reuse of metadata from maDMP (extracting to create SIP), suggested attribute: authoritative metadata	Repositories should be able to reuse (authoritative) metadata from other Information Systems, by harvesting, extracting, crosswalks etc.	
Files have not been evaluated for format appraisal (i.e. how suitable is the file format for digital preservation)	File format appraisal	File formats must have been evaluated for appraisal, indicating how suitable they are for preservation.	Evidence of how suitable different file formats are for preservation.

Appendix D: Scenarios for AIP Interoperability and Exchange

Table D.1 Scenarios for AIP Interoperability and Exchange

ID	Scenario	Description
I/AIP-SCEN-1	Exchange of AIPs between organisations and systems	<p>AIPs can be used as part of lossless exchange of content between TDAs and digital preservation environments. Reasons for transfer of AIPs between repositories or preservation systems include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transfer of custody from one repository or archive to another, for example if a repository is no longer capable of being the custodian of some or all of its holdings. • Migration of content between digital preservation environments, for example if a new digital preservation system is being installed to replace an old one. • Replication of content across multiple repositories, for example in a LOCKSS type approach where multiple organisations hold a copy of the same content for redundancy and resilience.
I/AIP-SCEN-2	AIPs as part of Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery (BCDR)	<p>Serialisation of content into AIPs that are then stored outside of a repository's main systems can form an important element of business continuity and disaster recovery. If a major failure or outage occurs in the main systems (for example, data centre disaster, ransomware, supplier goes out of business etc.), then a set of AIPs in an independent location can be used as part of recovery from the disaster. This is because the AIPs are self-describing and should contain all the information needed to understand the content within them and to continue the digital preservation of that content.</p> <p>This is sometimes called establishing a 'fire break'. If the whole repository 'burns down', then the AIPs in the external location should be unaffected, which then allows for recovery.</p>
I/AIP-SCEN-3	AIPs as evidence of following good practice for digital preservation	<p>Holding content in AIPs is not mandated by most models of good practice for long-term digital preservation. Instead, good practice for digital preservation tends to focus on the processes that should be followed (for example the Core Preservation Processes identified in EDEN) and the information that those processes create or consume. As defined in OAIS, an AIP should contain content information (e.g. the data and metadata that is the subject of preservation) and a full set of Preservation Description Information (PDI) (e.g. identifiers, checksums, rights, provenance etc.). This means an AIP both provides a record of the preservation processes that have been followed (e.g. provenance) and contains the artefacts of those preservation processes (e.g. file format identifiers, metadata from characterisation, normalised files). This in turn means that AIPs can be used to provide evidence that a TDA has applied good practices in digital preservation. The content they contain and the fact that they exist (or can be constructed) can provide assurance that good practice is being followed.</p>
I/AIP-SCEN-4	AIPs as evidence of a sufficient Information Model	<p>In OAIS, an AIP is part of the OAIS Information Model. This is a logical model that describes the information that should be managed / retained in an archive that conforms to OAIS. For example, an AIP should contain all the descriptive, structural, technical, administrative and technical metadata needed to fully understand the data in the AIP. This includes the semantics of the content plus supporting information such as checksums, file format information, a history of all preservation actions, licensing and rights and so on. Therefore, if a TDA implements AIPs that follow a recognised specification such as the OAIS Information Model, or if the TDA can show that its holdings conform to the requirements of the OAIS Information Model, then this can make it easier to assess whether a TDA is using an information model that is sufficient for digital preservation.</p> <p>As described by David Giaretta¹²⁰, who is one of the main authors of OAIS, "If an archive claims that it has Archival Information Packages (AIPs) then it must be able to identify, in whatever it calls its version of an AIP, all the various components which an OAIS AIP must have. If it cannot do this then it cannot be conformant to OAIS.". The converse is therefore that if an archive can show that it holds all the required components of an AIP as defined by OAIS then it is holding sufficient information according to OAIS that is needed for digital preservation and use of its holdings.</p>

¹²⁰ See David Giaretta's book Essential Digital Preservation as provided on the OAIS community wiki http://community.oais.info/Main/WebHome#Essential_Digital_Preservation_45_free_book